

FNS - Cloud

Food Nutrition Security

Food Nutrition Security Cloud

Deliverable 4.3

Tools and data requirements for assessing substances in foods: Development of the MCRA risk assessment tool and a consumer app

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D4.3 Tools and data requirements for assessing substances in foods

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Relevant IPRs	MCRA tool: RIVM Consumer app: BfR and PMT																																				
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Summary

Food may contain hazardous substances such as contaminants or residues from pesticides or food packaging materials. Food risk assessment requires many data (e.g. chemical concentrations, food consumption and health hazards). There are already well-established datasets (e.g. in EFSA collections), but also emerging datasets which can be very useful (e.g. data from total diet studies). Tools for food risk assessment are available, but require well-formatted input data. Data harmonisation and data conversion are therefore essential steps. Food risk assessment is complex and is constantly evolving, using more complex statistical approaches as the discipline develops. Therefore it is useful to develop demonstrator software to facilitate understanding and guide different identified user groups including risk assessors and consumers.

Task 4.3 of the FNS-Cloud project aims to create e-services that enable two examples of user communities, consumers and researchers/risk assessors, to evaluate and visualise chemical food safety data. Consumers will be able to use concentration data from total diet studies (TDS) within decision making processes in their daily life, e.g. in the supermarket when purchasing foods. High-end users, e.g. risk assessors and researchers, will be able to use TDS or monitoring data for higher-tier more complex risk assessments. Specifically, the latter approach will use the probabilistic assessment with the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) tool.

Within FNS-Cloud there are five phases in this process, split over WP 4 (Use cases) and WP 5 (Demonstrators), covering specification, implementation and testing (Task 4.3) and improvement and evaluation (in WP 5).

In this report four use cases are outlined, using the MCRA tool (three use cases) or a new consumer app (one use case). The emphasis is on the formulation of user requirements, i.e. describing how the systems requirements should work for specific scenarios, on the required functionality of the tools, and on data organisation connecting different data sources such that they can be used together in the assessments. For some use cases preliminary results from running the exposure or risk assessments are reported. Final results of the use cases will be reported in a follow-up report (Deliverable 4.4).

1 Introduction

Risk assessment of chemical exposure from food requires availability of data of different types: chemical concentrations in food products, food consumption, hazard characterisation, and possibly additional data depending on the complexity and realism of the risk assessment model. Such data typically stem from different origins. For example, chemical concentration data may be obtained from national monitoring programs on samples from retail outlets. Alternatively, chemical concentration data may originate from a more specific total diet study (TDS) where the sampled food has been prepared to represent as closely as practically possible the food consumed by consumers. Food consumption data are typically obtained from national food consumption surveys. Hazard characterisation data may be available in the form of established legal values, e.g. as acceptable daily intake (ADI) or tolerable daily intake (TDI), or it may be derived from more primitive data such as dose-response data by deriving no-observed effect levels (NOAEL) or benchmark doses (BMD) and applying additionally assessment or uncertainty factors.

In food risk assessment, it is important to select an appropriate model based on the type of chemical hazard. Some chemicals, e.g. some pesticides, can lead to acute health effects, e.g. neurological adverse outcomes. Other chemical, e.g. metals, are mainly of interest because of chronic health effects, due to long-term exposure. For both risk types different types of models are relevant as will be shortly described later in this document.

For risk assessment calculations the relevant data have to be combined. The FNS-Cloud project aims to implement and follow FAIR principles (findability, accessibility, interoperability, reproducibility) to allow data managers of diverse data (e.g. consumption data, TDS data) to organise their own data, and then bring these data together for analysis by an appropriate tool. In this work, we report on data specifications required to use the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) tool for probabilistic dietary risk assessment (van der Voet et al. 2020). Three case studies with MCRA are described, two for TDS-based risk assessments regarding risks of heavy metals, and one to illustrate mixture risk assessment. The aim of all three MCRA case studies is to improve the transparency of the data organisation and calculations, and to make this type of calculations available in future demonstrator software.

The first MCRA case study performs probabilistic risk assessment regarding the exposure of German children to methylmercury. TDS data are combined with food consumption data, and the method is developed to address stratification of the calculations regarding region, season and production type (organic or conventional).

The second MCRA case study performs probabilistic risk assessment regarding the exposure of Belgian children, adolescents and adults to nickel. TDS data are combined with food consumption data.

The third MCRA case study performs probabilistic risk assessment regarding the exposure of Dutch children to pesticides. EFSA monitoring data are combined with food consumption data. In this example the focus is on cumulative exposure, because different pesticides can have the same health effect and should therefore be combined in the risk assessment.

Furthermore, a new app is developed to transfer the FAIR data principle also to the consumer. Occurrence data of substances in foods will be made accessible for low-end users. Since contamination of foods is a sensitive topic regarding public perception, the app development is divided into two parts. The first one is the data preparation and the technical implementation of a test version. The second part will put the app to the test with low-end users and includes further improvements. Risk communication experts will support the process.

2 Original data

2.1 Concentration data from total diet studies and monitoring surveys

2.1.1 Introduction

Concentration or occurrence data for chemical substances in foods are an essential input for dietary exposure or risk assessments. There are many different types of concentration data, examples of which are:

- Food composition databases (FCDBs) which contain information on a wide range of components in food, including macronutrients (e.g. protein, carbohydrates, fat), minerals (e.g. calcium, iron, sodium) and micronutrients (e.g. vitamins). Lists of FCDBs are maintained by e.g. FAO/WHO¹ and by EuroFIR².
- Official control programmes for regulated substances. For example, the EU-coordinated control programme (EUCP) for pesticides³ randomly samples the food products most commonly consumed by EU citizens giving a statistically representative snapshot of the presence and concentration of pesticide residues in those products. In their annual reporting, EFSA also includes results from national programmes, implemented by regulatory authorities within individual countries/member states⁴.
- EFSA also collects data on contaminants in food⁵ and publishes them together with their opinions⁶. Contaminants are chemical substances that have not been intentionally added to food or feed. Other categories are food additives and food contact materials. All these substances may be present in food as a result of the various stages of its production, processing, or transport.
- The Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission has established the Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring (IPCHEM) as the EC's reference access point for chemical occurrence data in Europe⁷.
- Often concentration data are measured in samples of food which has not yet been prepared for human consumption. TDSs aim to provide more realistic data on food contamination and chronic exposure levels of relevant human populations (EFSA, FAO and WHO, 2011).
- Whereas most of the above mentioned data aim to monitor existing concentration levels, data may also be gathered in designed experiments or field trials using new chemicals (e.g. pesticides) for use in prospective risk assessments with the aim to obtain admission for future use.

In this report, the focus is on the data structures and datasets in the selected use cases, which are TDS data for metals and EFSA monitoring data for pesticides (Table 2.1). Each of the datasets is described in full below.

Table 2.1. Concentrations datasets in the use cases of this report.

Concentration data	Chemical(s)	Years	Data holder	Data owner
TDS-Exposure (German pilot TDS)	methylmercury	2014-2015	BfR	BfR
BfR MEAL Study	elements, including (methyl-)mercury	since 2015	BfR	BfR
INNIBEL	nickel	2017-2018	UGent	UGent
EFSA monitoring	pesticides	2014-2016	EFSA	Member States, Iceland and Norway

¹ <http://www.fao.org/infoods/infoods/tables-and-databases/en/>

² <https://www.eurofir.org/food-information/food-composition-databases>

³ https://ec.europa.eu/food/plants/pesticides/maximum-residue-levels/enforcement/eu-multi-annual-control-programme_en

⁴ [https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/toc/10.1002/\(ISSN\)1831-4732.CHEMICALRESIDUES-DATA#heading-level-1-2](https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/toc/10.1002/(ISSN)1831-4732.CHEMICALRESIDUES-DATA#heading-level-1-2)

⁵ <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data-report/chemical-contaminant-and-additives-occurrence-2011-2015>

⁶ <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/publications?f%5B0%5D=topic%3A349>

⁷ <https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

2.1.2 TDS-Exposure data (German pilot TDS)

A TDS was carried out by the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) within the framework of the European “Total Diet Study Exposure” (TDS-Exposure) project⁸. This pilot study provides mean occurrence data for the six elements aluminium (Al), copper (Cu), mercury (Hg) and methylmercury (MeHg), manganese (Mn) and lead (Pb) in the most frequently consumed foods by adults living in Germany. Details on the German pilot study are described in Kolbaum et al. (2019) and Tietz et al. (2019) and are summarised below.

The selection of the food list for the German TDS study was based on data from the National Consumption Survey II (NVS II) (Krems et al., 2006) conducted in 2005/2006, covering age groups 14 to <80 years. Selection criteria were: being part of at least 90% of consumption in each of the main food groups or being a significant contributor to dietary exposure regarding the selected elements. The latter choice was based on expert experience in risk assessment. In total, 246 foods were selected for analyses covering 95% of the total consumption. According to the TDS principles (EFSA, FAO and WHO, 2011) foods were analysed as pooled samples. In these pools, similar foods with expected low variability in the substances under consideration are aggregated. In the TDS-Exposure study, each pooled sample consisted of 12 individual foods (so called subsamples; e.g. 12 types of apples are homogenized to one apple pool representing the average apple consumption in the German population). Pools were assigned to food groups according to the FoodEx2 food classification system⁹ covering 18 of the 20 groups. As no data about child consumption were considered, the FoodEx2 main food group “Food products for young population” was not included. Likewise, the FoodEx2 main food group “Additives, flavours, baking and processing aids” was not represented in the pilot study because of its low contribution to overall consumption and dietary exposure to the selected elements.

Due to the pilot nature of the study, sampling was restricted to the Berlin area. A shopping list was prepared taking free available market share data on certain brands and types of foods on the German market into account. Grocery shopping took place between March 2014 and February 2015. For 20 items of the food groups vegetables, fruits, meat and fish, sampling was conducted twice in different seasons to account for seasonal variation (one season with expected higher local production and one season with expected higher import rates). The time point of seasonal sampling was defined individually for each sample according to seasonal calendars or available statistics. All other samples were taken once during the sampling period.

Based on the principles of TDS, foods were analysed “as consumed” to account for concentration changes during preparation and for industrially applied ingredients (e.g. preparation of cheese cake or frying of meat). The information on how the selected foods should be prepared was taken either by practices recorded in NVSII, or from recipes selected from two standard cookbooks on the German market or according to package information. After this preparation, subsamples were pooled and homogenised prior to analysis. Analyses were conducted in accredited laboratories (DIN EN ISO/IEC 17025), either by the National Reference Laboratory for Food Contact Materials at BfR or a contracted test laboratory. The complete dataset will be made available in a data repository either via FNS Cloud, as soon as respective structures are implemented, or will be linked to the FNS Cloud, when another repository is used.

2.1.3 BfR MEAL Study (Germany)

Using the experience from the pilot TDS, Germany established in 2015 the first full-scale TDS, the BfR MEAL Study (MEAL: meals for exposure assessment and analytics in foods). This study provides data regarding concentration for around 300 substances, divided in nine groups (elements and environmental contaminants, pesticides, perfluoroalkyl substances, nutrients, mycotoxins, pharmacologically active substances, process contaminants, food additives, substances migrating from food contact materials) in the most frequently consumed food in Germany (Bürgelt et al., 2016).

The selection of the foods was based on representative national consumption surveys: the National Consumption Survey II (NVSII) covering age groups 14 to < 80 years (as previously described in 2.1.2) and a German consumption data set for children called VELS (“Consumption Survey of Food Intake among Infants and Young Children”) covering age groups 0,5 to <5 years (Sarvan et al., 2021). In order to represent the German eating behavior, more than 90% of all foods reported to be consumed in these two surveys in Germany were included. Additionally, foods less consumed, but known for high concentrations of substances, were also included in the food list. The selection of these potential high contributors was based on expert judgements consulting experience of experts from different areas of food analysis, exposure assessment

⁸ <http://www.tds-exposure.eu>

⁹ <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data/data-standardisation>

and risk assessment. Through this process around 60,000 different foods, aggregated to ~4.000 pools, were selected. Pools were assigned to 19 food groups according to FoodEx2 (Stehfest et al., 2019).

In order to represent the purchasing behavior of German consumers, market share data from 2014 – 2017 on e.g. brands or varieties consumed by the German population were obtained from a representative household panel containing ~30,000 households. Furthermore, a market and social research institute was contracted to collect further information such as out-of-home consumption. The shopping list was compiled accordingly in order to representatively reflect the shopping behavior (Stehfest et al., 2019). Foods expected to vary little or not at all from region to region regarding composition and level of contamination (e. g. processed foods), were purchased in Berlin. Foods that were likely to have heterogeneous levels of contamination, depending on the purchasing region, are sampled regionally. Therefore Germany was divided into four regions (north, east, south, west). When assumed, a distinction was made between organic and conventional production. Mainly for fresh fruits and vegetables as well as for meat, foods are sampled in two seasons: one season with expected higher national production/pasturage and one season with expected higher import rates/indoor livestock farming (Hackethal et al., 2021).

Based on the principles of TDS, foods are analyzed “as consumed”. The inedible parts are removed, meaning bones and skin from meat or fish as well as peel, seeds, fruit stones from fruits and vegetables when these were not consumed. Fruits and vegetables are washed or peeled according to consumer behavior. Foods are prepared “as consumed”, e.g. cooked, pan-fired etc.. In order to prepare the food under consideration of typical German household behaviors, preferences regarding browning degree, sources of recipes, materials of used kitchen utensils have been also queried beforehand by a market and social research institute and taken into account in the preparation plan (Stehfest et al., 2019). Samples were aggregated to pools and homogenized for analyses. In the BfR MEAL Study one pooled sample is composed of 15 to 20 subsamples. The analysis of the abovementioned substances was performed in-house or by external certified laboratories (Sarvan et al., 2017).

2.1.4 INNIBEL study (Belgium)

The Innibel study ran from 2017 till 2019. A risk-based sampling plan was used to collect most relevant food products for nickel (Ni) occurrence/contamination from the Belgian market (Babaahmadifooladi et al. 2020). The sampling plan included different food categories. These food categories were classified as to plant-based products and their derivatives (effect of environmental contamination and the nickel presence in the structure of plant’s enzymes), canned foods/drinks (contamination from the package material), animal-based products (effect of nickel contamination from the environment), polyol containing food products (nickel contamination during the production process of polyols), beers (contact with stainless steel contact material during production) and processed foods (contamination during the production process from food contact materials). The results of the screening for foods present on the Belgian market are presented in the study (Babaahmadifooladi et al. 2020). In total 708 samples from different food categories were available. In brief, samples (N=708) were collected from retailers, markets or detail shops and they were analyzed in duplicate before their expiration date. The nickel concentration data were collected through the standard scientific analysis approach for trace elements (Babaahmadifooladi. et al. 2020). These data have been reported according to the EFSA format (Appendix 7.1.3.1.1) and the variables identification have been provided according to the chemical monitoring reporting guidance (2020 data collection) of the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA, 2020). This data is being currently used by EFSA in a new Ni exposure calculation and TDS (CONTAM panel – Katleen Baert).

According to the EFSA, FAO and WHO (2011) guidelines, the pooling type and degree of food products are highly dependent on the study purposes and the available budget. Besides, food products with highly different concentrations of the element should not be pooled (EFSA, FAO and WHO, 2011). Pooling should typically be conducted either via an individual food approach (pooling of different varieties, forms or brands of the same food merged into one food type) or a mixed food approach (several different foods belonging to the same food category such as different types of the fruits, e.g. apricot, apple and pear, were pooled together to obtain the mean nickel concentration for that main food category) (EFSA, FAO and WHO, 2011).

Therefore, both individual food types (11 groups - lower level) and food categories (8 groups - higher level) were used to conduct pooling of the food samples in this study. Beers, carrots, chocolate spreads, coffee, dark chocolates, iced tea, milk chocolate, peanut butters, potato, spinach, tomato and tomato sauces were pooled for different varieties, origin or brands, i.e. individual food product approach. For beers, legumes, breakfast cereals, dried fruits, nuts, soy products and tea drinks pooling was conducted according a mixed food category, e.g. chickpeas, lentils and beans were pooled to have

one mean nickel concentration for the legumes or drinks, tofu and dessert and cream are aggregated towards soy products, in total, 62 different food types are included in the MCRA food catalogue for the UGent case study (see Section 7.2.2).

2.1.5 EFSA monitoring data (Europe)

EFSA monitoring data used in these case studies, is extracted pesticide residue data from EFSA's data warehouse (EFSA, 2019b) which was collected over the period 2014-2016. The datasets captures occurrence data on 210 substances related to four health effects (two regarding the nervous system and two regarding the thyroid) and included data from all 28 European Members States and of Norway and Iceland. The occurrence data set was restricted to 30 raw primary commodities (RPCs) of interest (oranges, mandarins, apples, pears, peaches, table grapes, wine grapes, strawberries, bananas, potatoes, carrots, tomatoes, peppers, aubergines, cucumbers, courgettes, melons, broccoli, cauliflower, head cabbage, lettuce, spinach, beans (with pods), peas (without pods), leek, olives (oil production), oats, rice, rye and wheat). In addition, occurrence data of foods for infants and young children was included. For detailed descriptions see van Klaveren et al. (2019a, 2019b).

2.2 Consumption data

2.2.1 Introduction

Food consumption data are the other essential input for dietary exposure or risk assessments. The EFSA Comprehensive Food Consumption Database¹⁰ is a source of information on food consumption across the European Union (EU). It contains detailed data for many European countries. EFSA uses the food classification system FoodEx2 to categorise foods and beverages included in the database. Summary statistics are available in the EFSA Data Warehouse (EFSA, 2019b).

In this report, the focus is on datasets related to the selected use cases, namely the German, Belgian and Dutch national food consumption surveys for the specific age groups (Table 2.2 – details for each dataset are given in the sections below).

Table 2.2. Consumption datasets in the use cases of this report.

Consumption data	Country and population group(s)	Years	Data holder	Data owner
VELS	Germany, 0.5-<5 years	2001-2002	BfR	BfR
BNFCS	Belgium, 3-64 years	2014-2015	Sciensano	Sciensano
DNFCS	Netherlands, 2-6 years	2005-2006	EFSA	RIVM

2.2.2 VELS data (Germany)

The VELS study ("Consumption Survey of Food Intake among Infants and Young Children") is a national food consumption survey from Germany. The study provides a complete overview of the eating habits of infants and young children in Germany and can be used to estimate short- and long term dietary intake of food, nutrients and substances. VELS was carried out by University of Paderborn, in collaboration with the BfR between June 2001 and September 2002 and included 804 individuals, covering age groups from 0.5 up to 5 years (Banasiak et al., 2005).

In order to collect nationally representative data for this age group, participants were selected living in different regions across Germany with balanced distributions of ages and gender. Social status and residential area (urban or rural area) were also considered in recruitment. The field-study phase of the food consumption survey was carried out over a period of 15 months (June 2001-Sept 2002) in order to include seasonal variations in eating habits. Parents of the individuals recruited were asked to complete a precise recording of all consumed foods (raw or prepared) over six days in total. Recording period for each individual was divided (2x 3 days) with an interval of 3-6 months (for infants 4-8 weeks). The sizes of the portions were determined by weighing using scales before consumption and after, determining the amount consumed by subtracting remaining quantities from served amount. Food consumed out of home were also recorded

¹⁰ <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/food-consumption/comprehensive-database>

and quantities were estimated from the number of spoonful or portions, or, if it was known, as g or ml (f. e. branded products). Following completion, completed food consumption records were inputted and coded according to a national coding system.

2.2.3 BNFCs data (Belgium)

The official Belgian national food consumption survey (BNFCs) data, collected 2014-2015, belongs to Sciensano¹¹. In total, 3200 people were randomly selected and classified into 64 subgroups spread throughout the country to have geographical dispersion. The population density of every region was taken into account and the number of the selected people were proportional to the total population of the region. Every subgroup consists of three different age groups, i.e. children (3-9 years old), adolescents (10-17 years old) and adults (18-64 years old). In total, 1000 children, 1000 adolescents, and 1200 adults participated in the data collection. The consumption data were collected for 2 days (day 1 and day 2) for all participants using a 2x24h recall method. Body weight (b.w.) of all participants was also recorded.

Sciensano collected the consumption data with foods coded in FoodNum and FoodEx2 codes¹² (EFSA, 2021). Sciensano recommended to use the FoodNum system for conducting exposure assessment. For the current case study in the FNS-Cloud project, the raw and unprocessed Belgian FoodNum coded food consumption data were used and this FoodNum codes have been introduced into the concentration data as well (code conversion was needed). This was conducted in order to have as much as possible a match between concentration data and foods or recipes consumed by the Belgian consumers.

2.2.4 DNFCs data (Netherlands)

Food consumption data for Dutch children aged 2 to 6 years were derived from EFSA's comprehensive database (EFSA, 2011), which includes data from the DNFCs-Young children conducted in 2005 and 2006 (Ocké et al., 2008).

The consumption data used in this analysis was extracted by EFSA from the raw primary commodity (RPC) Consumption Database (EFSA, 2019a). The RPC Consumption Database was obtained by applying the RPC model to EFSA's Comprehensive Database. In the Comprehensive database, foods can be present as RPC (e.g. apple), an RPC derivative (processed RPC) (e.g. apple juice) or a composite food (e.g. apple pie). EFSA used the RPC model to transform the RPC derivatives and composite foods as present in EFSA Comprehensive database back to RPCs including facets describing the process applied to the RPC (e.g. juicing).

Two population groups were created by EFSA: toddlers: 2 year olds and the other children (3-6 year old). The group of toddlers consisted of 322 individuals, whereas the group of other children consisted of 957 individuals. The method used was a food recording on two non-consecutive days for each individual. The carer of each child recorded in pre-structured diaries the foods and drinks the child had consumed.

2.3 Other data

2.3.1 Catalogues

Chemical concentration data require a coding system for substances and for foods. Food consumption data require a coding system for populations and foods. In addition, mixture risk assessment requires a coding system for the relevant health effects. Substances, foods, populations and health effects are considered to be primary entities for dietary risk assessments.

Catalogues are datasets containing a complete enumeration of items needed within a specific context, here the use case. The items in a catalogue have unique identifying codes and typically have also more descriptive names and possibly more elaborate descriptions. Standard catalogues are available for substances, e.g. using CAS codes, InChi codes or EFSA PARAM codes, and foods, e.g. the FoodEx or FoodEx2 system or the Languag system. The EFSA Data Collection Framework

¹¹ <https://fcs.wiv-isp.be>

¹² <http://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/microstrategy/food-consumption-survey>

provides a collection of catalogues as is continuously being developed by EFSA¹³. In the case studies different coding systems were used, sometimes derived from coding systems related to the original data and sometimes ad-hoc (e.g. for populations and health effects).

2.3.2 Hazard characterisations

In the risk assessment analyses in this report, probabilistically assessed exposures were compared to standardised fixed values for hazard characterisation. These values were the acceptable/tolerable daily intakes (ADI/TDI) for the specified substances, and were obtained from EFSA's OpenFoodTox database (<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data/chemical-hazards-data>).

¹³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.779880>

3 Specifications and data to use the MCRA tool for chemical food risk assessment

3.1 Introduction

Computational tools to assess chemical food risks for human health need to compare a calculated exposure to a specific hazard level. The majority of available tools are simple and apply deterministic calculations, often using worst-case values to ensure a desired level of protection and thereby accepting of over-estimation (some examples are mentioned in the next paragraph). For more realistic estimations, tools that offer probabilistic models are used such as MCRA. In some situations, e.g. mixture risk assessment, probabilistic estimation is essential to avoid extreme compounding of over-estimations.

Often, tools are restricted to either exposure or hazard. For example, EFSA has developed a range of exposure or intake assessment tools for feed additives (FACE), food enzymes (FEIM), food additives (FAIM), pesticides (PRIMo) and food contaminants (RACE)¹⁴. As an example of a hazard characterisation tool, RIVM has developed the PROAST tool for calculation of benchmark doses¹⁵. In the case studies of this chapter the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) tool is applied, which is described in the next section. MCRA was developed by WUR and RIVM for national risk assessments and for EFSA, who have applied MCRA results in recent cumulative risk assessments for pesticides (EFSA et al., 2020ab).

3.2 The MCRA platform

3.2.1 Introduction

MCRA considers risks from chemical substances and mixtures in relation to human health using probabilistic models, typically a two-dimensional Monte Carlo approach to address variability and uncertainty distributions in the data being used in the analysis e.g. food consumption, or contaminant levels. MCRA is a web-based system for hazard identification, hazard characterisation, exposure assessment and risk assessment, which applies this probabilistic approach to risk assessment. The MCRA system brings together a system which houses statistical models and analytical tools, along with shared data and a system to support use of data uploaded by the user.

MCRA 9 was developed in EU project EuroMix (2015-2019) and also in a partnership between EFSA, RIVM and WUR (2018-2020) to assess risks from combined exposure to multiple chemicals from multiple routes of exposure using deterministic and/or probabilistic methods. MCRA 9 has 51 modules which address all major areas of risk assessment, and includes a data repository with data collected in the EuroMix project. MCRA 9 is available for registered stakeholders at <https://mcra.rivm.nl>. MCRA version 9 and the EuroMix data repository have been described in more detail in van der Voet et al. (2020). See also additional online documentation at <https://mcra.rivm.nl/Documentation>.

In the FNS-Cloud project, MCRA will be made available as a web service in the FNSCloud infrastructure. Demonstrator projects will demonstrate how the service can be used, and will also allow prospective users to perform probabilistic risk assessments themselves. A further objective is to implement interoperability with data providing platforms.

3.2.2 Probabilistic models in MCRA

Humans consume foods in variable amounts on different days, and the average consumption is variable between human individuals in a population. Chemical substances that may have adverse health effects are thus present in variable amounts in the consumed foods. For realistic exposure and risk assessments it is relevant to take account of these variabilities as well as of the uncertainties that arise if the data are limited. MCRA offers probabilistic models that take

¹⁴ <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/science/tools-and-resources>

¹⁵ <https://www.rivm.nl/en/proast>

into account this distribution of exposure and the resulting distribution of risk. For an introduction to the exposure models in MCRA, see Boon and van der Voet (2015).

Depending on the nature of the adverse health effect, MCRA can describe the variability of exposure between individuals (for chronic risk) or between individual-days (for acute risks). In the case studies in this report, heavy metals like methylmercury and nickel are addressed as examples of chronic risk assessment, whereas pesticides that can have neurological effects are an example for cumulative acute risk assessment.

In the acute risk case, the available data for consumption and for concentrations in the consumed foods are randomly resampled and combined in a Monte Carlo procedure with for example 100,000 iterations. In the chronic risk case, it is assumed that concentration variability will average out over the long-term, such that only the variability in food consumption is relevant to assess the long-term exposure distribution.

For chronic exposure assessment, MCRA offers several probabilistic models, varying in complexity and realism. In this report we will use a simple, distribution-free method, known as Observed Individual Means (OIM), where the observed exposures on the individual-days of the consumption survey are simply averaged to values per individual. It is important to note that the OIM model will overestimate the upper tail of the exposure distribution if the number of survey days per individual is small. This is a well-known bias and was previously confirmed in simulation studies (Goedhart et al. 2012). Several alternative and more realistic models are implemented in MCRA, which rely on distributional assumptions, typically the assumption that positive individual-day exposures amounts are distributed normally after an appropriate data transformation (e.g. a log transformation). The most used MCRA model in this category is the LogisticNormal-Normal (LNN) model, which allows to model absence/presence of exposure with a logistic normal distribution and the positive amounts by a normal distribution on the transformed scale. Other models are also available, for which we refer to tutorial report mentioned above (Boon and van der Voet 2015) or to the MCRA Documentation.

For risk assessment, exposures have to be compared to values that characterise the toxicological hazard. MCRA also offers extensive possibilities for hazard modelling, from simple deterministic to probabilistic. In this study, the attention is restricted to the use of deterministic, regulatory hazard characterisation values, such as the ADI or ARfD, and variability and uncertainties in the hazard characterisation will not be addressed. In this simple model, the exposure distributions will be converted to risk distributions in the form of a hazard index, where exposures are simply divided by the regulatory hazard characterisation value.

Finally, in real life, health effects can be caused by multiple chemicals, and this requires the use of cumulative exposure and risk assessment. MCRA implements the dose-addition model where exposures of single substances are combined in a weighted sum, with relative potency factors (RPFs) as weights. RPFs are typically obtained from dose-response experiments. MCRA allows the use of RPF data or the calculation from dose-response data.

3.2.3 Data formats MCRA

For chemical dietary risk assessment, Table 3.1 gives an overview of the data needed in MCRA. The data organisation of MCRA in line with the modules and each data module has an associated data type consisting of one or more data tables. Further details of the MCRA data formats are given in Appendix 7.1.1.

Table 3.1. Overview of data in MCRA for dietary risk assessment.

Category	Tables	Description
Catalogues	Foods catalogue; Food hierarchies catalogue; Food processing types catalogue	Definition of relevant foods (consumption, concentrations); assignment of foods to main food groups; definition of food processing types
	Substances catalogue	Definition of the chemical substances which present hazards
	Populations catalogue; Individual properties; Population individual property values	Definition of the population(s) to be protected

	Effects catalogue	Definition of the relevant adverse health effect(s)
Concentrations	FoodSamples; AnalyticalMethods; AnalyticalMethodSubstances; SampleAnalyses; Concentrations or: ConcentrationsSSD	MCRA supports input of occurrence/concentration data in several formats, among which is the EFSA SSD format. Internally, MCRA works with a relational table schema composed of a samples table, defining the samples of the concentration data, a sample analyses table describing the analyses performed on the food samples, an analytical methods and analytical method substances table describing the analytical methods used by the sample analyses, and a concentrations table in which the concentration values of the sample analyses are recorded. When uploading, e.g., SSD data, MCRA will internally convert the data to this format.
	FoodProcessingFactors	Processing factors are multiplication factors to derive the concentration in a processed food from the concentration in an unprocessed food and can be specified for identified processing types (e.g., cooking, washing, drying).
Consumptions	FoodConsumptionSurveys; Individuals; Consumptions	Consumption data is described using three main tables: a table of food survey definitions, a table containing the individuals linked to the food survey definitions, and a consumptions table specifying the consumptions of the individuals of the survey.
Hazard characterisations	HazardCharacterisations	Toxicological reference value(s), e.g. ADI or TDI

3.3 Case study risk methylmercury for German children

3.3.1 Introduction

In this use case, a chronic probabilistic exposure and risk assessment has been performed on the intake of methylmercury (MeHg) by German children (ages 0.5 – <5 years) through consumption of foods from the food groups fish and seafood and mushrooms. Since no data from the BfR MEAL Study were available at the time point of writing the deliverable, data from the German pilot TDS (TDS-Exposure) (2.1.2) were taken and structured according to the data structure of the BfR MEAL Study (2.1.3). This was done, because the BfR MEAL Study with its comprehensive design offers more evaluation options. For the assessments the concentration data (mg MeHg kg⁻¹ food) data will be combined with food consumption data for children (g food day⁻¹) from the German VELs study (2.2.2). The individual body weights will be considered to obtain the exposure in µg kg⁻¹ body weight day⁻¹. The exposure will be compared to the tolerable weekly intake (TWI) of MeHg.

The above mentioned datasets were selected as a first example of manageable size. In the BfR MEAL Study, fish and mushroom were sampled proportionately in different regions but no further stratifications such as season were applied. In this case study stratifications also for season and type of production (organic or conventional) as well as more regional samples were artificially added. This adapted dataset was needed to test new implemented evaluation strategies in the MCRA software. Therefore all stratifications presented in this case study are artificial and the shown data will not reflect the actual contamination situation evaluated in the BfR MEAL Study, and are for illustrative purposes only. Next to the

implementation of the evaluation of different stratifications in a TDS, the below defined scenarios will further test other required implementations. The required implementations are summarised as follows:

1. Subset selections: Population
 - Selection of the properties region, season and breast-feeding as additional properties in the population subset selection
 - select of multiple population sub-groups for one MCRA run (simultaneous assessment and output in one loop)
2. Subset selections: Substances
 - Selection of multiple substances for one MCRA run (simultaneous assessment and output in one loop)
3. Subset selections: Foods
 - Inclusion of a food hierarchy to facilitate the selection of foods under consideration
4. Subset selections: Concentration data
 - Selection of the properties region, season and production type (organic or conventional)
5. Output optimization:
 - presentation of exposures on different hierarchical levels (e.g. pooled samples level and main food group level)

3.3.2 Scenarios

Five different scenarios are described to be tested in this case study. These are firstly the evaluation of the overall exposure assessment without consideration of any stratification (Scenario 1). Testing regional, seasonal and production type exposure (Scenarios 2 – 4). Finally, the combination of several types of stratifications in one calculation (Scenario 5).

In cases where no information on the distribution of organically or conventionally food choice in a population is available, the one or the stratification should be used only. Therefore, the scenarios in this case study consider conventional food choice as default setting for production type (if not indicated otherwise).

3.3.2.1 Scenario 1: Overall exposure from conventional foods

Distinct calculations for particular stratifications are not always required and the aim is to get an overview about the exposure situation in a population. Therefore, the first scenario will test the calculation of the overall long-term exposure of MeHg from all foods included in the dataset (fish, seafood, mushrooms and products thereof) in different age and sex groups of non-breastfed children from Germany at all ages (<1 to <5 years). Conventional food choice is selected as indicated above. The scenario can be summarised as followed:

$$\text{Concentration}_{\text{national, non-seasonal, conventional}} \times \text{Consumption}_{\text{national, non-seasonal}}$$

Only consumers of the mentioned foods will be considered in the analysis. The modified lower bound (mLB) and upper bound (UB) approach will be used for treatment of left-censored data¹⁶. In the mLB approach, censored values reported as 'below the limit of detection (LOD)' are replaced by 0, and values reported as 'between LOD and limit of quantification (LOQ)' are replaced by LOD. The UB approach replaces values below the limit of reporting (LOR) with the respective LOR.

¹⁶ left-censored data: measurements below the LOD or below the LOQ, but it is unknown by how much (also called non-detects)

Objective: Evaluation of the selection strategy when different stratifications need to be grouped (see specific requirements). Testing of the output of different population sub-groups in one loop and extraction of main contributors to exposure on different aggregation levels.

Specific requirements for implementation in MCRA: Since foods in the BfR MEAL Study can be multiply stratified (e.g. the item “apple” is sampled in different regions, and within this regions also in different seasons), the MCRA application must allow the grouping of multiple stratified foods for the overall exposure assessment (e.g. generate a mean concentration for the item “apple” from multiple stratifications). To allow the assessment in the mL approach, the implementation of using the LOD and LOQ as alternative options is identified as a future requirement, since in the current MCRA version just one threshold (LOR) can be defined for the selection of bounds.

3.3.2.2 Scenario 2: Regional exposure from conventional foods

Regionally assigned foods are sampled in four different regions: East, South, West and North Germany. Samples are taken in each region in equal proportion (no weighting factor needed). For the remaining foods non-regional (“national”) samples are taken (sampled around the Berlin area). For a refined exposure assessment, the combination of consumption and concentration data at the regional level is necessary. Therefore, the second scenario will test the calculation of the long-term exposure to MeHg in children from North, East, South and West Germany, respectively. For this assessment just consumers of fish and seafood and the UB approach will be considered. The seasons remain unspecified (non-seasonal) and the conventional food choice is used as default as described above. The scenario can be summarised as followed:

- Matching regional samples with regional consumption

$$\text{Concentration}_{\text{regional, non-seasonal, conventional}} \times \text{Consumption}_{\text{regional, non-seasonal}}$$

Objective: Evaluation of matching strategy regarding regional sampling and regional consumption. Testing of the implementation of selection of consumers only for the main food group fish and seafood.

Specific requirements for implementation in MCRA: In the BfR MEAL Study the stratification into regional samples was considered just for selected foods (e.g. the item “apples” is sampled in four different regions, whereas the item “banana” is just sampled once at the “national” level). For region specific exposure assessment, also the nationally sampled foods need to be included into the calculations to avoid underestimation. For example, when an exposure assessment for children in west Germany is selected, then the MCRA software needs to use the concentrations from the samples taken in west Germany as well as the concentrations from the samples taken at national level. Furthermore, the consumption from children living in west Germany needs to be matched with the respective occurrence data.

3.3.2.3 Scenario 3: Seasonal exposure from conventional foods

The definition of seasons in the BfR MEAL Study is described in section 2.1.3. Since these are very specific for the TDS model used in Germany and evaluation strategies are still in development, it was decided to focus on a seasonal stratification according to seasons of a year. For this exercise a stratification with just two fixed seasons was chosen:

- Season 1: Summer season (April-September)
- Season 2: Winter season (October-March)

Consequently, this scenario addresses long-term exposure to MeHg in children during summer and winter seasons. This scenario will consider just consumers of mushrooms and the UB approach. The regions remain unspecified (at national level) and the conventional food choice is used as default as described above. The scenario can be summarised as followed:

$$\text{Concentration}_{\text{national, seasonal, conventional}} \times \text{Consumption}_{\text{national, seasonal}}$$

Objective: Evaluation of matching strategy regarding seasonal sampling and seasonal consumption. Testing of the implementation of selection of consumers only for the TDS pooled foods mushrooms and products thereof.

Specific requirements for implementation in MCRA: In the BfR MEAL Study the stratification into seasonal samples was considered just for selected foods (e.g. the item “apple” is sampled in two different seasons, whereas the item “milk chocolate” is just sampled once at a random time of the year). This distinction between seasonal and non-seasonal foods also needs to be considered for this use case. This means, for season-specific exposure assessment, also the non-seasonally sampled foods need to be included into the calculations to avoid underestimation. For example, when an exposure assessment for children consuming foods during summer is selected, then the MCRA software needs to use the concentrations from the samples taken during summer season as well as the concentrations from the samples marked as non-seasonal. Furthermore, the consumption during summer season needs to be matched with the respective occurrence data.

3.3.2.4 Scenario 4: Exposure from different production types

Selected foods of the BfR MEAL Study food list are defined to be of organic production or conventional production. In this case, two pooled samples are taken for the selected foods: exclusively organically produced foods or exclusively conventional produced foods. All other (unspecified) samples are purchased according to market shares or availability on the market. These samples may include a mixture of organic and conventional produced foods. This scenario aims to compare long-term exposure to MeHg from consumption of conventionally or organically produced foods. Just mushrooms and products thereof will be included in the analyses. The UB approach will be calculated. The regions and seasons remain unspecified. The scenario can be summarised as followed:

- Matching conventional samples with national consumption

$$\text{Concentration}_{\text{national, non-seasonal, conventional}} \times \text{Consumption}_{\text{national, non-seasonal}}$$

- Matching organic samples with national consumption

$$\text{Concentration}_{\text{national, non-seasonal, organic}} \times \text{Consumption}_{\text{national, non-seasonal}}$$

Objective: Evaluation of matching strategy regarding the type of production.

Specific requirements for implementation in MCRA: In the BfR MEAL Study the stratification into organically or conventionally produced foods was considered just for selected foods (e.g. for the item “apple” a pooled sample with exclusively exclusively produced apples exists as well as a pooled sample with exclusively conventionally produced apples. Whereas the item “chewing gum” is sampled “non-specified” according to market shares). This means, for a production type-specific exposure assessment, also the non-specified sampled foods need to be included into the calculations to avoid underestimation. For example, when an exposure assessment for children with mainly organic food choice is selected, then the MCRA software needs to use the concentrations from the organically produced samples as well as the concentrations from the samples marked as non-specified.

3.3.2.5 Scenario 5: Combined stratification exposure

The above mentioned scenarios describe assessments with focus of one defined stratification. However, also the combination of different stratifications in one assessment can be of interest. Therefore, this scenario will calculate the long-term exposure to MeHg from consumption of mainly conventionally produced mushrooms and products thereof from West German samples consumed by children from West Germany during winter season. Just consumers of mushrooms and products thereof will be considered and UB approach will be calculated. The scenario can be summarised as followed:

- Matching conventional samples from region West and winter season with consumption from region West during winter season.

$$\text{Concentration}_{\text{region_west, season_winter, conventional}} \times \text{Consumption}_{\text{region_west, season_winter}}$$

Objective: Evaluation of matching strategy regarding the combination of several stratifications.

3.3.3 Data formats original data

3.3.3.1 Consumption data: VELs data format

The BfR uses consumption data from the VELs study (section 2.2.1). A detailed description about the contained variables is listed in Appendix 7.1.2.1. The following information is contained in four distinct SPSS files:

1. Consumed amounts (g) per food for each individual and on each reporting day. Foods are coded using a specific German food coding system (sbels-format) (7.1.2.1.1: Individual consumption).
2. Information on whether a child was breast-fed or not (7.1.2.1.2: breast-feeding).
3. Anthropometric and sociodemographic details per individual (7.1.2.1.3: Individual characteristics).
4. Information on how many reporting days were completed by each individual (7.1.2.1.4: Individual survey days).

The VELs data are available at BfR and will be made publicly accessible after implementation of respective infrastructures in the FNS Cloud.

3.3.3.2 Concentration data: BfR MEAL Study data format

The concentration data of the BfR MEAL Study is collected in excel files in a standardised results report. A detailed description about the contained variables is listed in 7.1.2.2.1: Results report.

The report contains analytical sample codes, sample names, substance, LOD and LOQ per sample, unit, analytical method and fields for eight possible analytical results, with special fields indicating whether a result was quantified or below LOD or LOQ.

Analytical samples are coded with a BfR MEAL Study data specific coding system. Substances are indicated with their substances names (no coding) and analytical methods are described with their technical abbreviations (e.g., LC-MS/MS).

Data were generated at BfR. After publishing, data will be publicly available upon request at the BfR MEAL Study homepage¹⁷.

3.3.3.3 TDS composition data: BfR MEAL Study data format

Information about the BfR MEAL samples selected for the use case and the respective mapping to the VELs consumption data are provided as excel files. The foods in the BfR MEAL Study are coded in a MEAL specific coding system. The MEAL food code describes the selected food included in the MEAL foodlist (e.g. for apple). The sample codes include further information about the stratification of the pooled sample (e.g. for apple, region west). MEAL code and sample code are provided together with information about the respective pooled amount (7.1.2.3.1: BfR MEAL Study Samples)).

The mapping table (7.1.2.3.2: BfR MEAL/VELs-Mapping table)) assigns the consumptions from the VELs study to the respective MEAL code. The coding from the VELs study (sbels codes) is mapped to the coding of the MEAL food (BfR MEAL Study coding).

3.3.4 Compilation of MCRA datasets

In order to run the exposure assessments in MCRA, the VELs consumption data, MEAL concentration data, and all other necessary data should be converted to the MCRA data formats. For this case study, three MCRA datasets are constructed:

- **Catalogues FNS Case Study MeHg DE Children:** a dataset containing the catalogues and secondary input data required for the dietary risk assessments of the scenarios. It contains the definitions of the populations, foods, substances and effects. It also contains a hazard characterisations table with the TWI that is used as a reference value for the risk calculation.
- **VELs Consumptions 2001-2002:** a dataset containing the VELs consumption data, recoded in the MCRA data format.

¹⁷ <http://www.bfr-meal-studie.de>; at the time of the deliverable the infrastructure for the public use file is under development.

- **Artificial MeHg Concentrations FNS Case Study:** this is a dataset containing the concentration data and information on the TDS sample compositions used for the dietary risk assessments of the scenarios.

The compilation of these dataset is performed offline, and the datasets are manually uploaded to the MCRA platform where they can be used for running different TDS exposure assessment scenarios.

The conversion/compilation of the datasets was automated by writing dedicated python conversion scripts to map the original data files provided by BfR to the MCRA data format. By doing so, the original data remains intact and all mapping steps and conversion decisions are stored within the conversion script, making the conversion process reproducible and more transparent than manual conversion. For more information see Appendix 7.2.1. The python scripts are available as supplementary material to this report.

3.3.5 Preliminary results

Final results will be presented in a follow-up report (Deliverable 4.4, due May 2022). This section outlines preliminary results about the progress of this work. The outlined scenarios were selected in order to test required evaluation options for the TDS functionality in MCRA. First implementations were tested in several test and feedback loops between BfR and WUR.

The functionalities according to the defined requirements outlined in 3.3.1 were tested during the first implementation cycles. This section will describe the new implemented functionalities:

1. Subset selections: Population

The additional properties region, season and breastfeeding were introduced to the consumption data and uploaded to MCRA. The respective selection options were itegrated in the user surface and can be selected together with other individual properties like age or gender (Fig. 3.3.1)

The option to select multiple population sub-groups for one MCRA run (simultaneous assessment and output in one loop) is in progress.

Figure 3.3.1. Selection of population

2. Subset selections: Substances

The selection of substances is implemented (Fig. 3.3.2). In the use case, just MeHg is included in the dataset. The selection of multiple substances is implemented and was already tested with another dataset. The use of multiple substances for calculations in a loop is in progress.

Figure 3.3.2. Selection of substance

3. Subset selections: Foods

A food hierarchy was implemented to select either whole food groups (e.g. fruit and fruit products), composite or pooled foods (e.g. apple compote) or consumed foods (e.g. apple compote) or consumed foods (e.g. apple compote with raisins, homemade) for the evaluations.

By selecting a main food group, all pooled samples assigned to this group will be used for the exposure assessment. If just particular pooled samples are of interest, these can be selected at the lower aggregation level. The lowest level is the selection of the foods as consumed. This is useful to select consumers of foods, which are aggregated to a pooled sample. For example, when different oilseeds are pooled to one sample “oilseeds”, but the assessor is interested in the exposure from sunflower seeds. In this case, just the consumption from sunflower seeds can be selected and matched to the concentration from the TDS pool oilseeds.

The hierarchical selection is implemented (Fig. 3.3.3). Further structuring for a facilitated selection process is in progress.

Figure 3.3.3. Selection of foods

4. Subset selections: Concentration data

Subset selections on concentration data site are implemented for regions, seasons and production types. The implementation also offers the option to include or exclude unspecified samples (non-seasonal, non-regional or unspecified production). Harmonization in the selection options are in progress.

Figure 3.3.4. Selection of samples

5. Output optimization

The output provides information about the selected percentiles and information about uncertainty (by resampling loops) in tables and graphs. In Fig. 3.3.5 percentiles 50 and 95 of methyl mercury exposure to children in the German population are presented as tables and box plot.

After implementation of loops over various population groups (e.g. different age groups) or substances, the results can be seen and downloaded (as csv. files) in one (or more) table(s) after one single run. This will accelerate and facilitate the handling of extensive datasets.

Figure 3.3.5. Preliminary results percentiles of exposure methylmercury

A new implementation also includes the presentation of exposures on different hierarchical levels. This allows the user to assess/interpret the exposure on main food group level or on composite food level (TDS pooled samples level). Minor optimisations of this output are in progress.

Figure 3.3.6. Preliminary output: contributions to exposure by food at different food group levels.

In conclusion, all basic applications considering the stratification strategies for running scenarios 1 to 5 are implemented and working. Some adaptations for facilitated use are needed and will be completed for Deliverable 4.4. The implementation of population and substance loops is in progress to enable quick assessments over various substances or populations.

3.4 Case study risk nickel for Belgian age groups

3.4.1 Introduction

In this use case, a chronic probabilistic exposure and risk assessment is performed on the intake of nickel by Belgian consumers (in several age groups) through consumption of foods from various food groups. For these exposure and risk assessments, TDS concentration data structured according to the data structure of the INNIBEL study (2.1.4) are combined with consumption data from the Belgian national consumption survey (2.2.3). The exposure is compared to the TWI for nickel.

In the original INNIBEL study, a probabilistic risk assessment on nickel in foods for Belgian consumers was conducted on the demand of the Belgian ministry of public health. Dietary exposure calculations aggregating over consumed foods were performed. Two days consumers (i.e. people who consumed every food for two consecutive days) and mean consumption over two days per subject were taken into account. The consumption quantities (g) of the consumers were divided to their body weight (b.w., in kg). A simple distribution approach according to EFSA, FAO and WHO (2011) was used, which is the same as the Observed Individual Means (OIM) model in MCRA. The mean nickel concentration (µg Ni g⁻¹ food) in every food category was multiplied to the mean consumption of every subject (g food kg⁻¹b.w. day⁻¹) for that food category. Further, all the exposures per food category were aggregated for every subject. Further, one exposure

distribution was obtained for overall exposure of subjects as data points. This was done twice for the nickel concentration data that was obtained through lower bound (LB) and upper bound (UB) scenarios. The mean, median, minimum, maximum, P70, P90, P95 are calculated according to LB and UB scenarios for the total consumers' population and its different age groups, i.e. children, adolescent and adults, in SPSS (IBM SPSS statistics, version 24) (Babaahmadifooladi et al. 2020).

A clarification regarding the coding system used for this case study and the original Ni concentration data is given here. In Ni concentration data that are available in the EFSA database, the FoodEx2 coding system was applied and this data has been uploaded in MCRA initially. However, it was needed to translate this coding system to the FoodNum coding system that was available in the Belgian consumption data 2014. The FoodNum code system was recommended to be used for conducting the exposure assessment by the data owner (Sciensano). Therefore the translation table was provided (as a complementary input) into MCRA to make it possible to have the best output from the software.

FoodEx2 is a comprehensive food classification and description system developed and maintained by EFSA to keep it up to date and cover data collection needs in different domains. While the FoodNum system was provided and created in Belgian food consumption data by the data owner institution (Sciensano). This coding system was much simpler than the FoodEx2 coding system entailed only numbers as a code and less data classification layer (hierarchy). The aforementioned concentration and consumption data (section 2.1.4 and 2.2.3) will be used to conduct the probabilistic calculation in MCRA 9.1, computing chronic exposure and risk using the observed individual means (OIM) model (3.2.2). The specific characteristics of the case study are summarised in Table 3..

Table 3.1 Case study specifications for the Belgian Nickel risk assessment.

Module	Required selection	Outcome
Foods	FoodNum codes in concentration and consumption data	Will be obtained based on Food categories and Food types.
Population	Children	For age group 1 (3-9 years)
	Adolescent	For age group 2 (10-17 years)
	Adults	For age group 3 (18-64 years)
	General consumers	Age group 1, 2 and 3
Substances	Nickel	Single element study
Dietary exposures	chronic	For two days consumers
Consumptions modelled food by	Consumers only	Non-consumers will not be included
Concentration models	UB/LB	similar results are expected
Modelled foods	no restriction	
Exposure	Mean and percentiles	

	Main contributors	Percentage contribution to the overall exposure
	Overall exposure for the consumers of listed foods	Mean and percentiles
Correction of the exposure outputs	Bioaccessibility percentages for selected foods	Mean exposure per food category or food types
Hazard characterisations	Updated TDI value (EFSA, 2020)	reference value
Risk	Comparison of selected exposure percentiles to TDI	Reference value exceeded or not

3.4.2 Scenarios

In the case study, assessments for different population groups and different analysis settings will be tested:

- Scenario 1: overall (aggregated) chronic exposure and risk assessment (all age groups / general consumers population) both UB/LB, for all foods
- Scenario 2: same as scenario 1, but per age group
- Scenario 3: contributions per food group (both UB and LB)

The exposure calculations will be conducted at a lower level of the coding system hierarchy (**Food types**). As previously mentioned, this will be done using the **FoodNum** codes as well as the **NAME** variables available in the extracted consumption data. This classification was opted by use according to the information that we wanted to get from the results. For instance, we decided to use all the FoodNum related codes for Legumes under one large category so-called legumes. However, for some categories like vegetables, we were interested to see the contribution of every vegetable such as carrot, tomato, and spinach separately so we specified the exposure results for any of them separately. It is good to mention the pooling the foods for conducting the exposure calculation is totally arbitrary and can be done according to the study purposes.

3.4.3 Data formats original data

The concentration data are available in EFSA SSD2 format in MCRA. The relevant variables for the data extraction have been summarized in Appendix 0.

The extracted consumption data (that are immediately available for exposure calculations) are available according to the FoodNum coding system. As previously mentioned, the FoodNum system is the coding system developed by Sciensano (data owner) and was recommended and used for exposure assessments and was more comprehensive than the FoodEX codes data (since 2021). Accordingly, FoodNum coding system was introduced into the Nickel concentration data as well. In this way both consumption and concentration data has the same coding system for use in MCRA.

3.4.4 Compilation of MCRA datasets

To run the different exposure assessment scenarios in MCRA, the BNFCs consumption data, INNIBEL concentration data, and all other necessary data should be converted to the MCRA data formats. For this case study, three MCRA datasets are constructed:

- **Catalogues FNS Case Study Nickel BE population:** a dataset containing the catalogues and secondary input data required for the dietary risk assessments of the scenarios. It contains the definitions of the populations, foods, substances, effects. It also contains a hazard characterisations table with the TWI that is used as a reference value for the risk calculation.
- **BNFCS 2014-2015 (FoodNum):** a dataset containing the BNFCS consumption data, recoded in the MCRA data format with foods coded by FoodNum codes.
- **Concentrations nickel BE (INNIBEL):** this is a dataset containing the Nickels concentration data.

FoodNum codes that will be available in consumption and concentration data will be used for running the case study. For translating the coding system of these data for MCRA, the catalogue of FoodNum codes will be introduced to the software. In this way, the software can recognize the codes and run the exposure calculations properly. Briefly, this leads to three MCRA-formatted data files that are used in the case study: consumptions, concentrations, catalogues. Details are given in Appendix 7.2.2.

3.4.5 Preliminary results

3.4.5.1 Substance names, codes

Substance	Substance name
RF-000001	Nickel (Ni)

3.4.5.2 Dietary exposure

The FoodNum codes were introduced to the concentration data and this version of the concentration data together with the codes catalogue were uploaded in MCRA. The obtained results (all calculations) for LB and UB are highly close so the obtained results will be shown only for UB.

The TDI for nickel is 13 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{d}$. The calculated exposure distribution in Figure 3.4.1 shows that exposure of the Belgian population is very variable across individuals (factors over 1000 are seen), but generally stays below the TDI level.

Figure 3.4.1. Exposure distribution (graph total).

3.4.5.3 Contribution to total exposure distribution for foods (as eaten)

In more detail, the exposure to nickel originates from many consumed food products, with chocolate spread, potatoes and tomatoes being primary sources (Figure 3.4.2).

Figure 3.4.2. Contribution to total exposure distribution for modelled foods for total population.

3.4.5.4 Results per age-group

In MCRA, the probabilistic risk calculation can be restricted to subpopulations. Three separate runs were performed for Belgian children (3-9 years), adolescents (10-17 years) and adults (18-64 years).

Figure 3.4.3. MCRA interface to access the results for three population groups.

Belgian children had exposures that approached but not exceeded the TDI of 13 µg/kg bw/day (Figure 3.4.4). Chocolate spread was by far the most important source of nickel intake (Figure 3.4.5).

Transformed exposure distribution (96.0% positives)

Cumulative exposure distribution (96.0% positives)

Figure 3.4.4. Exposure distribution (graph total) for children.

Figure 3.4.5. Contribution to total exposure distribution for modelled foods for adolescents.

Belgian adolescents had exposures that approached but not exceeded the TDI of 13 µg/kg bw/day (Figure 3.4.6). Chocolate spread, tomatoes and potatoes were the most important source of nickel intake (Figure 3.4.7).

Graph total

Transformed dietary exposure distribution (93.6% positives)

Cumulative acute dietary exposure distribution (93.6% positives)

Figure 3.4.6. Exposure distribution for adolescents (graph total)

Contribution to total exposure distribution for modelled foods.

Figure 3.4.7. Contribution to total exposure distribution for modelled foods for adolescents.

Belgian adults had generally lower exposures per kg bw than children and adolescents (Figure 3.4.8). Green tea and various types of chocolate were the most important source of nickel intake (Figure 3.4.9).

Transformed exposure distribution (68.8% positives)

Cumulative exposure distribution (68.8% positives)

Figure 3.4.8. Exposure distribution for adults (graph total)

Figure 3.4.9. Contribution to total exposure distribution for modelled foods for adults.

3.5 Case study risk of pesticide mixtures for Dutch children

3.5.1 Introduction

In this use case, acute and chronic probabilistic exposure and risk assessments are performed for exposure to pesticide mixtures by Dutch children through consumption of foods. For these exposure and risk assessments, concentration data from EFSA monitoring surveys (2.1.5) are combined with consumption data from the Dutch national food consumption survey (2.2.4).

EFSA's Panel on Plant Protection Products and their Residues (PPR Panel) published several opinions on the methodologies for calculating cumulative risks. A basic consideration in cumulative risk assessment is the identification of cumulative assessment groups (CAGs), defined as groups of pesticides causing the same toxic effects in tissue, organs and physiological systems that can produce joint, cumulative toxicity – even if they do not have the same mode of action

(EFSA, 2013). In 2008, the panel adopted an opinion on the suitability of existing methodologies for cumulative risk assessment of pesticides and proposed a tiered approach (EFSA, 2008), which was then applied to a selected group of triazoles (van Klaveren, 2009). In 2012, the EFSA Guidance on the use of probabilistic methodology for modelling dietary exposure to single and multiple pesticide residues was published (EFSA, 2012). Two different basic model runs for exposure assessment were proposed: an optimistic and pessimistic model run, leading to upper and lower estimates of the true distribution of exposure. The outcome of both model runs can be used to determine whether further refinement of the exposure assessment is useful (EFSA, 2012). The European Commission (EC) and Member States started discussing risk management aspects related to the assessment of cumulative exposure. As a result, the EC Standing Committee on Plants, Animals, Food and Feed (SC PAFF) agreed on the following changes during its meeting of 11-12 June 2015:

- Instead of the basic optimistic and pessimistic runs, and refined modelling as proposed in the EFSA guidance of 2012, a new tiered approach will be introduced;
- Tier 1 modelling will consist of a model run with conservative assumptions, instead of one optimistic and one pessimistic run.
- Tier 2 modelling will consist of a model run with more realistic, but still conservative, assumptions and sensitivity analyses to better understand the uncertainties.
- The results of the cumulative exposure assessment will be expressed in terms of Margin of Exposure (MoE).

The use of these tiers by EFSA was requested in a letter from the EC to EFSA¹⁸, informing that during the SC PAFF meeting of 18-19 September 2018, the Member States agreed on certain assumptions concerning risk management aspects of the assessment of cumulative exposure in a retrospective scenario (related to monitoring data in food). These tiers will be referred to in this report (and in MCRA) as EC 2018 tiers 1 and 2.

Organising data and providing intended model specifications can become very cumbersome due to the complexity of the modelling. Therefore, the FNS-Cloud project aims to add an additional layer to the MCRA tool by developing interfaces, called standard actions, for (partly) predefined data and model settings. For the mixture risk assessments of this use case, calculations have already been organised in standard actions to allow an easier use of MCRA.

Table 3.2 Case study specifications cumulative exposure assessment of pesticides by Dutch children

Module	Required selection	Outcome
Foods	RPC food codes in concentration and consumption data	
Population	Toddlers	For age group 1 (2 year olds)
	Other children	For age group 2 (3-6 years)
Effect	NAN	Acute effect on the nervous system: neurochemical effects
	NAM	Acute effect on the nervous system: functional effects on the motor division
	TCP	Chronic effects on the Parafollicular (C)-cells or the calcitonin system

¹⁸ http://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/SANTE_CRA_Mandate.pdf

	TCF	Chronic effects on Follicular cells and/or thyroid hormone system
Substances	Multiple pesticides	Multiple pesticides
Dietary exposures	acute	Exposure per consumption-day
Consumptions modelled food by	Whole population	Non-consumers will be included
Concentration models	MB	½ LOQ or 0 for non-detects depending on percentage positives found in monitoring data
Modelled foods	no restriction	
Exposure	Percentiles:	50, 75, 90, 95, 97.5, 99 and 99.9
	Main contributors	Percentage contribution per food and substance to the upper tail exposure
Correction of the exposure outputs	Adjustment factor based on parameters obtained from expert elicitation regarding uncertainties for exposure and hazard	Mean exposure per food category or food types
Hazard characterisations	NOAEL	For each substance a NOAEL (No observed adverse effect level) is provided. One substance is marked as index substance. For each substance a relative potency factor is calculated.
Risk	MOET	MOET < 100: might be a possible risk

3.5.2 Scenarios

Functionality for mixture risk assessment is required according to the EC 2018 tiers 1 and 2. Consequently, these tiers have been implemented in MCRA and their use for EFSA application is illustrated in the mixture risk assessments for pesticides that could affect the neurological system or the thyroid (van Klaveren et al., 2019ab). The data organisation for these higher-tier assessments requires expertise and is not easy to perform. Another issue concerns limitations on the data availability of the consumption data at the individual level, which restricts possibilities to share the data organised in the work for EFSA. For the use case in this report, the scenario to be elaborated was the availability of a demonstration dataset, that can be used to illustrate risk assessment for mixtures of pesticides. The functionality was organised as a standard action in MCRA. In a standard action, all or most input data and all or most settings are already predefined which makes a standard action easier to use than an action where all inputs have to be organised from scratch. The data used have been described in detail.

3.5.3 Data formats EFSA

All data used in this case study were provided by EFSA. A short description of the consumption, occurrence and processing factors data is given here. All data were coded following version 4 of the EFSA Data Collection Framework (DCF) catalogues¹⁹.

The RPC Consumption Database was obtained by applying the RPC model (EFSA, 2019a) to EFSA's Comprehensive Database (EFSA, 2011). In the Comprehensive database, foods can be present as raw primary commodity (RPC) (e.g. apple), an RPC derivative (processed RPC) (e.g. apple juice) or a composite food (e.g. apple pie). EFSA used the RPC model to transform the RPC derivatives and composite foods as present in EFSA Comprehensive database to RPCs including facets describing the process applied to the RPC (e.g. juicing).

Each year, the 27 EU Member States, the United Kingdom²⁰, Norway and Iceland report results concerning pesticide residue monitoring to EFSA. Data is sent to EFSA using the SSD2 format. The data is stored in EFSA's Data Warehouse. EFSA extracted the data for all residue definitions present in the CAG for the years 2014-2016. The occurrence data set was restricted to thirty raw primary commodities of interest for the cumulative exposure assessments. In addition, occurrence data of foods for infants and young children was included.

Occurrence data is (mostly) reported at the level of the raw primary commodity (e.g. apple), whereas consumption data might also be reported on the processed level (e.g. apple juice) or as a composite food (e.g. apple pie). The level of the active substance can change as a result of processing. By using a processing factor, this can be taken into account. EFSA extracted processing factors for the substances belonging to the CAGs and the commodities of interest from the EU processing factor database (Scholz, 2018).

The users of the case study might want to upload own occurrence (see table 4) or processing factors data (see table 5) to combine with the already organised data in this standard action. This is foreseen to be implemented in the nearby future. When organizing own data users should be aware to prepare data according to the format mentioned in paragraph 3.5.4. Foods present in the occurrence data should be coded using the Matrixcode present in the MTX catalogue. Substances should be coded using the Param catalogue.

3.5.4 Compilation of MCRA datasets

Data received from EFSA were included in MCRA tables (see van Klaveren et al., 2019, Appendix D). All data are available in the standard action. The user of this case study can either select data from EFSA or organise the data in the requested MCRA formats. In the nearby future it will be possible to organise own occurrence and/or processing data to use in the standard action. When a user also wants to organise other data this should be done by using a custom action in MCRA. A user should organise all necessary data tables as described in van Klaveren et al., 2019, Appendix D.

3.5.5 Preliminary results

Final results will be presented in a follow-up report (Deliverable 4.4). Here some preliminary results are presented.

In MCRA it is possible to create a standard action (see Figure 3.5.1).

EU acute cumulative exposure assessment (2018) Tier I and Tier II

This standard action will enable you to reproduce the exposure assessment of acute cumulative effects of pesticide residues in food affecting the nervous system. These are retrospective exposure assessments of the cumulative exposure for the nervous system using monitoring data from 2014, 2015 and 2016. In this standard action Dutch monitoring and consumption data are used. The results, data used and methodology are reported in a scientific report following published on the EFSA website in September 2019. The methodology fulfils the requirements set by the European Commission.

Figure 3.5.1. Standard action EU acute cumulative exposure assessment (2018) Tier I and Tier II.

After creation of the standard action a user has several options for the settings (see figure 3.5.2). At the moment it is not possible yet to use own consumption, occurrence or processing data, but this might change in the future.

¹⁹ All EFSA DCF catalogues can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.779880>.

²⁰ Occurrence data included in the assessment were submitted to EFSA when the UK was a member of the EU.

EU acute cumulative exposure assessment (2018) Tier I and Tier II
Standard action - EU acute cumulative exposure assessment (2018) Tier I and Tier II

Settings

EU acute cumulative exposure assessment (2018) Tier I and Tier II

This standard action will enable you to reproduce the exposure assessment of acute cumulative effects of pesticide residues in food affecting the nervous system. These are retrospective exposure assessments of the cumulative exposure for the nervous system using monitoring data from 2014, 2015 and 2016. In this standard action Dutch monitoring and consumption data are used. The results, data used and methodology are reported in a scientific report following published on the EFSA website in September 2019. The methodology fulfils the requirements set by the European Commission.

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Exposure assessment settings Saving...

Tier / calculation method
EC 2018 Tier 2

Effect
NAN

CAG
Full CAG

Population
Netherlands-Toddlers

Uncertainty analysis
No uncertainty

Individuals subset Save Changes

Individual subset selection

Figure 3.5.2. Options for different settings when using the standard action.

After saving the selected settings a simulation can be started and when this is finished the results can be viewed. The results are presented in tables and graphs (see figure 3.5.3 and 3.5.4).

Percentiles margin of exposure.

Percentage exposure	Exposure (µg/kg bw/day)	Percentage MOE	Margin of exposure
99.90	2.431	0.10	41.14
99.00	0.6062	1.00	165
97.50	0.3341	2.50	299.3
95.00	0.2199	5.00	454.8
90.00	0.1547	10.00	646.4
75.00	0.09777	25.00	1023
50.00	0.06202	50.00	1612

Figure 3.5.3. Result of the simulation: exposure and MOE at different percentiles.

✓ Upper tail exposures by food and substance

Total 225 combinations of foods and substance with contribution in the upper tail. bw/day.

Contribution to the upper tail distribution for modelled foods x substances (MSCC).

Figure 3.5.4. Result of the simulation: main contributors to the exposure.

3.6 Conclusions on MCRA case studies

Considered collectively, the three case studies with MCRA have demonstrated the available opportunities to perform probabilistic (i.e. more realistic) assessments of exposure and risk than are usually available from deterministic calculations. The ability to perform such calculations is available in a web-based platform (MCRA) that can be linked to the FNSCloud infrastructure.

An important conclusion is that data organisation is never easy. Data availability is often dependent on access conditions which may be project dependent. Technically, different datasets (such as consumption and concentration data) originate in world of their own, with non-harmonised coding systems and data formats. Therefore, harmonisation and data conversions are an essential part of the work to realise the case studies.

Probabilistic calculations can become complex in terms of data needs and model specifications. In FNS-Cloud the aim is to achieve examples of practical use in demonstrator projects. In MCRA, such demonstrators will be realised using specifically optimised user interfaces known as standard actions.

The case studies and their implementation in demonstrator projects will be addressed in a follow-up report (Deliverable 4.4, due May 2022).

4 Development of a new consumer app for occurrence data of substances in foods

(Responsible partners: BfR and PMT)

4.1 Introduction

The purpose of TDSs is to measure the quantity of substances in foods “as consumed” over the entire diet. Results of these studies are the basis for food chemicals / additive / contaminant risk assessments conducted by national institutes. However, the datasets used and generated within these analyses are not usually available for the general public, resulting in a perception of lack of transparency. Even if datasets were to be made generally accessible via data repositories or institutional platforms, the public may not be able to find, understand and use them. Problems in this context are the lack of knowledge about existing data, the retrievability of data and, overall, the complexity of the datasets which makes it impossible for non-experts to access the knowledge.

On the other hand, consumer interest in nutrition and health policy is growing, and the use of apps is increasing and successfully applied. Therefore, the option to obtain knowledge about food chemical contents might also be of interest to some consumers. As argued by Sir John Krebs: “Consumers are entitled to information that could affect health, and transparency helps them to make informed choices” (Krebs, 2003). Thus, in terms of transparency and FAIR data, a consumer app using TDS data was considered for development under consideration of the differing perception of food safety information by low-end users in contrast to e.g. nutrition related information.

4.1.1 Objective of the app

The app will be developed to inform users about content data of contaminants and residues in food. Accordingly, the app is aimed for low-end users (e.g. consumers) or, more specifically, to the part of users with interest or concerns regarding nutrition and health-related topics. This includes consumers with substance-related health issues, e. g. intolerances.

Informing the user includes two aspects:

- a) Using results of Total Diet Studies, which are also applied as basis for risk assessments and should therefore be transparent and available for the user.
- b) In addition, the data provided needs to be put in context so the user is able to understand and use relevant data to make informed decisions.

People’s intentions to download and use the app will differ than the usual use of TDS data which is to inform national and European regulatory authorities. Instead, people are going to use the app with the intention to obtain knowledge with regard to substances in food. In addition to their expectations (app will help to answer questions), other key reasons to use health-related applications are costs (app should be free of charge), design (being visually appealing) and a clear arranged menu navigation (Kramer, 2017) and should be considered as well.

As it is already decided which dataset(s) will be used, concept options to meet users expectations are limited: TDS-datasets can be arranged by foods (all contents of analyzed substances in one specific food) or by substance (occurrence of the specific substance in all considered foods). Accordingly, some possible expectations can not be realized. For example, the concept of TDS does not allow comparisons of foods of different brands. In addition, the app cannot be used for individual risk assessments and exposure estimations because of the high complexity of calculation, which might be seen as a disadvantage especially by consumers expecting personalized information using the app.

4.1.2 Scenarios

With regard to the objectives and the structure of TDS, the two possible ways for consumers to use the information were considered and part of preceding deliberations. Accordingly following scenarios were designed which are the basis of the concept of the app and will be tested in WP5.

Scenario 1: Does my food contain high contents of contaminants or residues?

In the first scenario, the user might have read a statement from the national public health authority, an article in newspapers or the internet/social media or heard from friends about the occurrence of contaminants or residues in a specific food. Especially if the source of information is not an official one, informed consumers might be wondering if the information is true. Possibly they want to learn more about it or about possible actions.

Accordingly, the app will be used to search for a given food in order to obtain information about the concentration of substances in the specific food. In addition the user should be able to rank the contents by comparing the content data with other foods to make an informed dietary decision.

Scenario 2: What is this substance and where does it occur?

A consumer might hear about an emerging food risk or “trending” contaminant from the media and might be worried about the health. Or they or family members have health-related issues with a specific substance. The user should be able to find the substance in the app, get clear and reliable information about the substance and its occurrence in foods.

Scenario 2a

Scenario 2b

4.1.3 Challenges & risk communication issues

Generally, the development of a mobile app based on statistical and scientific information faces user-friendliness-related issues such as:

- Presentation of complex datasets on small screens
- Understandability of figures, statistical evaluations and text segments

The development of a mobile app based on results of TDS faces additional issues. As food safety is a growing concern of the (lay) general public (Tucker et al., 2006; EFSA, 2019), presenting data of potential harmful substances may produce risk communication-related issues. Transparency in the communication of food risks in general is widely debated as it is seen to be helpful for the (lay) general public to make informed choices and generates trust in the authorities, but on the other hand it may at the same time also cause confusion because of scientific pluralism, and lack of knowledge on the topic (Lofstedt, 2006; Jansen, 2019).

Therefore several risk communication-related issues, mainly concerning used vocabulary and phrases, have been considered (modified by Jansen et al. (2019, 2020a, 2020b)):

- Scientific jargon and phrasing: may be difficult to understand and can easily be misunderstood
- Negative associations exist with specific words, and as such need to be avoided and/or explained
- Phrasing: explicit mentioning of specific characteristics of substances can be understood as the substance is a hazard (“because if not, it would not be mentioned”)
- Vague, ambiguous language: may lead to misinterpretations
- Oversimplified representation due to technical limits of food safety issues may lead to misinterpretation of the data

Several recommendations are mentioned in the publications (Jansen et al., 2019, 2020a, 2020b), including the involvement of the target group in the app development, reflection of the meaning of the used terms for the target group and a clear and exact communication of facts to evoke incorrect conclusions.

In accordance with these recommendations, to the named general and target-related issues, a far-reaching test and feedback-strategy is already underway and planned. For example, with regard to possible issues with the design of the app or rather challenges to present complex datasets on small screens, usability tests with colleagues are planned. Additionally, the test strategy will involve feedback rounds in order to deal with risk communication-related issues. Constant feedback-rounds with experts of risk communication are already in progress. The concept of the app, including simple statistical analysis, are under evaluation. All included text segments (e. g. explanations, disclaimers) will be reviewed by the experts. Selected consumers and further low-end users (potential professional users that are not experts for TDS concept or exposure assessment) will be involved in the usability testing.

Nevertheless, it has to be kept in mind that risk perception might differ between populations of different countries and national bodies need to consider local conditions in their risk communication or applicability of such an app.

4.1.4 Procedure

The development of the app consists of several steps: First, the data, provided by TDS needs to be evaluated, to consider reasonable arrangements for presentation on small screens of smartphones – the likely use of the app. These deliberations were included in the initial planning discussions and drafts. At the same time considerations were made about the required additional information and simple statistical analyses which would be needed for users to understand and use the data provided.

The evaluation of this additional information and analyses with regard to possible risk communication issues, arising from the use of the application, is part of all current and following development steps and feedback rounds. On basis of the initial drafts, the β -version of the app has been implemented/developed, which represent the current status of the app and will be described in following sections. Currently, improvements of the β -version are in progress in consultation with experts of risk communication of BfR. Some results of these expert feedback rounds will already be mentioned in following sections.

Improvements of the β -version will be included in the 1st version, which will be evaluated later by colleagues from the BfR with focus on technical aspects and in further feedback rounds with experts of risk communication with the focus on challenges and chances of this channel of data communication, as part of WP5.

Further improvements and the implementation of the 2nd version, as well as usability tests including selected consumers, other low-end users as described in 4.1.3. as well as risk communication experts will also be part of WP5 and therefore briefly be described in section 5.2.

4.2 Implementation of the β -Version

In the long-term the app will provide a platform for use of TDS data from several countries. Therefore, the design needs to align with general TDS data structures and be multilingual. However, for the purpose of this pilot launch, the structure and data will be taken from the German pilot TDS dataset (TDS-Exposure) (see section 2.1.2). Further improvements as part of WP5 will be made taking into account the structure and extent of data of the first German full-scale TDS (BfR MEAL Study (Sarvan et al., 2017)) with the option to adjust to other TDS designs. In addition, language of the β -version is English. The app will be translated into German as part of WP5 (see section 5.2).

4.2.1 Design

Taking into consideration the complex datasets presented in the app, the design needs a clear and user-friendly interface, including simple, recurring user interface elements. In addition, the structure of the app needs to align with the objective of FNS-Cloud-Project and possible questions the user might have (scenarios presented above). In accordance with the designed scenarios (4.1.2), the app will be divided into three parts, which are connected when appropriate:

- Food View
- Substance View
- Dataset

The sections “Food View” and “Substance View” are designed to be the major options, through which the consumer will enter the app (see scenarios above) while the section “Dataset” provides basic information with regard to the respective TDS supporting the app and information provided.

As potential users will have varied background knowledge, it is important that each section provides “easy-to-find”/“easy-to-understand” information, sufficient for answering questions of the respective scenario. For interested or advanced users, further information will then be further provided.

The following sections will describe how the data of TDS will be presented in the two major sections of the app. Additional considerations with regard to improvements of usability and interpretability of the content data by the user will be described briefly, considering the respective benefits and risks. In accordance to the current development status, some sections, which are still under review in this β -version will be improved for the implementation of the 1st version.

4.2.1 Food View

The section “Food View” was designed with regard to scenario 1 (4.1.2). The user is able to search for a specific food in order to get the respective content data of all analyzed substances. Therefore, in this section, results of Total Diet Studies are sorted by foods.

This objective was implemented as follows:

With regard to the design of the app, the user is able to search for the food of interest by entering the name or by using search options (e. g. useful if the spelling is not known correctly or the food has different names depending on the region). The user will be directed to a graph with content data of all analyzed substances (in TDS Exposure) in the food of interest.

[on the left: example for search entries; by selecting “filter” the user will be directed to search options]

[on the right: after the selection of a food, content data are presented; here: illustrated as example are content data of all six substances, analyzed in TDS-Exposure, in asparagus in one graph]

Presenting the content data aligns with the objective of the development to make TDS data available and transparent. However, by just presenting the data, it is questionable if the user will be able to interpret or use the data in any meaningful way. This leads to the question how the user can be supported by providing additional information to support understanding and use of the data. Various possibilities were considered and discussed with experts of risk communication:

- a. Comparison of the content data with toxicological reference values
 - b. Comparison of content data with average content data of the respective food group
 - c. Comparison of the content data with other foods
- a) The first option (a) seems to have the great benefit that users might directly see the relation of the content of the substances in the given food and the respective toxicological reference values. However, this option was evaluated to carry great risks. This presentation ignores the fact that normally many foods in any given diet contribute to the total exposure towards any substance. For example: comparing the copper content in apples (0,05 mg/ 100g) with the respective upper intake level (adults: 5 mg/ day) could lead to the conclusion that 10

kg apples can be consumed to reach the upper intake level. This conclusion was even drawn in the expert feedback round. However, as copper is an ubiquitous occurring element, all other foods also contribute to dietary exposure but are not considered in this presentation. In addition this option requires calculations on the part of the users, especially if the reference values are related to the weekly intake of substances. Therefore, no comparison between content data in a single food and toxicological reference values will be presented in the app.

- b) The idea of the second option was to show if the contents of the substances in the given food are high or low compared to other foods. Some substances occur mostly or exclusively in a specific food group (e. g. nitrate in leafy vegetables), thus comparing content data of single foods with average content data of all analysed foods might lead to false conclusion or rather has no informative value (f. e. comparing nitrate content of spinach with average content data of all foods including dairy products, meat and other food groups without any nitrate). Therefore, it was discussed with the experts of risk communication to allow comparisons of content data of single foods with average content data of the respective food group. This allows a broad classification of the contents in the given food. No risks have been identified by the experts with regard to this option. Therefore it is planned to include this comparison in the app.
- c) The idea of the third option was not only to enable the user to understand if content levels are high or low (in comparison to other foods in a given food group) but also to give the user options to make informed decisions. Therefore it was considered to be helpful to allow comparisons of single foods. However, this option was discussed to be problematic with regard to the question, which foods should be compared. The comparison of foods just on basis of some contaminants and/or residues ignores other desired or undesired ingredients in the foods. Therefore it was first planned to allow just comparisons of foods within the same food category. But, as user might not want to substitute a food by a food of the same food category, also a comparison between food categories will be made possible. A disclaimer will be embedded (“Please keep in mind that this information allows no generalized statement regarding nutritional and health value of the mentioned foods. For an overall assessment, all ingredients, as well as the belonging to certain groups of the food pyramid, should be considered.”). A link to respective food pyramid is planned.

4.2.2 Substance View

The section “Substance View” was designed with regard to the scenario 2 (4.1.2). For this section, data of TDS are not sorted by food, but by substance. This allows the search for a specific substance and its occurrence in various foods. Equally to the food search, the user will be able to search the substance by name and given search options.

Initially it was planned to present the user a fact sheet with a short description of the substance, basic nutritional and toxicological information and results and simple analysis from the respective Total Diet Study. This concept was, as part of the β -version, discussed with experts of risk communication. They expressed concerns regarding some sections of the fact sheet (described below) and, more particular, with regard to the structure. The fact sheet as planned would imply that users read every section in order to make an informed decision. Therefore it was decided to change the concept and to initial show a short statement and the table with contents in foods:

- “easy-to-understand” statement: information whether toxicological reference values (and, when relevant: intake recommendations) are reached with regard to the population-based exposure assessments (the exact text is still under consideration and will be reviewed by experts of risk communication)
- Table: contents of the substance of interest in single foods, in descending order and arranged by food groups

[on the left: example for search entries; by selecting “filter” the user will be directed to search options]

[on the right: after selecting the substance of interest, the user will be directed to content lists, arranged by food group; presented are exemplary aluminium content data in individual foods of food group “fruits and products”]

This presentation of content data in foods aligns with the objective to make TDS data available. In addition, users may already benefit from this presentation as they get the information which foods contain high contents of the given substance, a useful information with regard to food intolerances. However, beside presenting the results of Total Diet Studies, providing further explanations or information might be useful with regard to different background knowledges and interests of the potential users. Various options were considered and discussed with experts of risk communication:

1. Short description of the substance

As demonstrated in scenario 2a, a comprehensive background knowledge cannot be presumed. Users might just have developed an interest in a specific substance because of some hearsay. Therefore, it might be helpful to provide the user (optional) with some scientific-based background knowledge regarding occurrence of the substance, entry path into the foods and significance for humans. Information will be mainly based on statements and opinions of EFSA. This section was considered as unproblematic by the experts of risk communication and will therefore be included in the app. However, text segments will be revised for comprehensibility.

2. Nutritional and toxicological information

In addition to the background information regarding the significance of the substance of interest for humans, it was discussed whether and how to include further nutritional and toxicological information. Following details have been under consideration:

- a. Essential – Presentation of information on whether a substance is essential or not for humans was considered as important and should (additionally) be included in the short description of the substance but might also be mentioned in this section.
- b. Reference Values - Contrary to direct comparison of individual content data with reference values (section “Food View”), there were less concerns presenting the data as background information without direct comparison with individual content data. However, it must also be considered that one prevented users drawing comparisons, making an examination of benefits and risk of this information necessary. In addition to described concerns, benefits for users with little or no background knowledge or further interest might be low. However, incorporating reference values could be considered an enormous gain for highly interested users as self-contained searches are work-intensive. However, the reason why these values will be included in the 1st version

of the app is transparency. As already described, the incorporation of a short statement is planned, based on reference values. Therefore, it is necessary to include the reference values to explain the background of this statement.

- c. Population based exposure assessments - In addition to the reference values, the initial statement is based on population-based exposure assessments. In order to be transparent about the basis of the statement, respective exposure assessments need to be included. However, the presentation of population-based exposure assessments offers opportunities but also entails some challenges or concerns mainly related to the correct understanding. A major opportunity of the presentation of estimated exposures beside transparency is, for the user to get an idea whether there is a high, population-based, intake of the substance of interest. However, presenting exposure assessments also bears the challenge that users might take the population-based exposure assessments as their individual intake, leading to possibly unnecessary actions in order to decrease (or increase) their intake. In consultation with the experts of risk communication it was decided to include the simplified exposure assessments and to evaluate them in planned tests with potential users. In addition, an explanation will be included, among others, describing that presented values do not represent individual exposure.

As a reaction to the initial statement, the description of the substance or the population-based exposure assessment, users might want to know how to adjust their individual intake. Based on the initial list with contents of the substance of interest in foods arranged by food groups, users will be able to identify the foods of each group with highest or lowest contents. However, this approach bears the risk that consumers are focused on foods rarely consumed (with regard to the respective consumption survey). Therefore it could be relevant to also present which foods contribute to the dietary exposure. For example, content of various substances are highest in spices (e. g. manganese: 9,25 mg/ 100 g), but because of its low consumption, contribution to dietary exposure is low (<0,1%). This evolved into the concept of presenting the contribution to dietary exposure (calculated from consumption and content data). Two possibilities were considered: the presentation of the contribution of single foods or of food groups to dietary exposure. Presenting contributors on single food level offers the benefit that users can directly see which food(s), on basis of content and consumption, should be avoided in order to reduce the intake. For example, based on content data and average consumption, main contributors to dietary exposure to lead are wine (13-14%), vegetable salad (10-11%) and multigrain bread (6%) (Kolbaum et al., 2019). However, just around 20 foods contribute to dietary lead exposure with more than 1%. Therefore, this presentation was considered to be problematic especially for ubiquitous occurring substances as the contribution of single foods to total exposure is low. As a second option it was considered to present the contribution of food groups to dietary exposure (e. g. food group “composite dishes” are main contributors to dietary lead intake with 18,60-19,70%, followed by “alcoholic beverages” with 16,80-18,10%). The benefit of this presentation is that users can see which food group(s) are relevant and therefore check the respective content tables. However, similar to the presentation of population-based exposure assessments, the presentation of simple analysis for possibly uninformed users on a small screen bears the risk that data will not be understood or false interpreted. Therefore an explanation will be provided and reviewed by experts of risk communication. Also, the understanding of these analysis by the user will be included in planned tests.

4.2.3 Datasets

As Total Diet Studies are mainly unknown by the public and by the potential users, the app will provide some basic information about the respective study. For interested users, further information are available as links to corresponding webpages, publications or other relevant information sources.

[on the left: example for a short description of a TDS considering basic information and special features of the respective study and a brief summary of TDS principles]

[on the right: example for further information with regard to the respective TDS, among others: links to publications and websites]

4.3 Technical implementation details

The consumer app will be developed as a web app (test version at <https://tds.test.fns.foodcase-services.com>), that can be accessed via an internet browser both on smartphones and computers/laptops. The original plan was to implement a mobile app so that consumers have it on their smartphone and do not need an internet connection. Web apps can be developed in a mobile first approach which means that they are first and primarily designed for smartphone devices where screen size is limited and content must be limited and compactly condensed. In addition, responsive web design (RWD) allows to adjust the layout and content of web pages depending on the screen size. A different layout can be used on small screen such as smartphones, than on medium size screen such as tablet and on big screens of laptops and monitors. Another limitation of mobile apps is that different smartphone platforms exist and separate implementation must be done to cover them all except if some special framework like PhoneGap are used. It was therefore decided to implement the consumer app as web app and not mobile app using a mobile-first approach and a responsive web design. The advantage is that the graphical representation of data is much better visible on big screens. HTML5 also allows for offline applications which also remove the disadvantage of web apps for needing an Internet connection.

The consumer app uses a three layer architecture with a front-end part running in the web browser while a back-end part running on the server with a separate layer for the database. The frontend (user interface) will be implemented using Angular and will communicate with a Java backend (data storage and management) application. The front-end application will communicate with backend by a REST-full API. The backend application will be created based on Spring Boot framework. Data access will be realized by Spring Data and Hibernate ORM. PostgreSQL database will be used for data storage and management.

4.3.1 Database diagram

For the database, the following entity-relation diagram is implemented. The core entities are the food, substance, and substance_measurement entities where the substance_measurement entity is between the food and the substance. There is also an entity to group food into categories and the food, substance and category entity have a translation table to have data in different languages.

4.4 Preliminary results

As the development of the app is still in progress, this section will summarize the achievements so far under consideration of named challenges, user-scenarios and objectives of the app. With regard to the procedure described before (4.1.4), currently the β -version was implemented and discussed in first feedback-rounds with experts of risk communication.

Basic concept and design

The basic concept and *design* was defined. The user will have to possibilities to enter the app by searching a specific food or by searching a specific substance. In addition to the respective results of the TDS (contents of all analysed substances in the specific food or contents of the selected substance in all analysed foods), simple statistical analyses and TDS-independent information will be provided. The user should be able easily find the basic, as most important considered information with the option to obtain more detailed and specific information. This concept was already discussed with experts of risk communication and will be implemented in the 1st version.

Scenarios

As part of FNS-Cloud project it was already preliminary decided which dataset(s) will be used. Therefore, no proceeded surveys were conducted in order to determinate possible questions of potential users. However, on behalf of the datasets it was deliberated, which questions can be answered and properly *scenarios* were designed (4.1.2). With regard to scenario 1, the user is able to search for the food of interest and directed to the content data of analysed substances in the food. As for the β -version, German pilot TDS “TDS Exposure” (2.1.2) is used, all content data will be presented in one graph. Additionally, users get the option to compare content data of the specific food with average content data of the respective food group, single foods of the respective food group and every food analysed in the Total Diet Study.

With regard to scenario 2a and b, the user is able to search for the substance of interest. Initially a short statement (“easy-to-understand”) whether toxicological reference values (and, if relevant: intake recommendations) are reached with regard to the population-based exposure assessments. Users (scenario 2a) might decide at this point if they are interested in more information. Additionally, contents of the substance in all foods, sorted by food groups, will be shown and especially answer questions of scenario 2b. If more information is required or users want to know the background of the initial statement, they get general information about the substance, reference values and simple statistical analysis regarding the population-based dietary exposure and the contribution of food groups to the estimated exposure.

Challenges and risk communication

With regard to the named risk communication-related *challenges* (4.1.3) some progress have been made although there are still additional feedbacks needed in order to detect possible pitfalls before testing the app with the consumers. Summarized, following issues with regard to the initially named issues were discussed and handled and/or planned to be included in further expert feedback rounds:

- *Scientific jargon and phrasing: may be difficult to understand and can easily be misunderstood*

The app will be developed in order to present scientific results complemented by scientific-reliable information. Definitions for used terms and presented facts about substances are taken from EFSA glossary or EFSA statements or opinions if available. Accordingly they might include inconclusive statements, understood by experts but not by the general public (Jansen, 2019, 2020a). In addition, scientific jargon is associated with increased risk (Jansen, 2020b). In order to avoid misunderstandings, texts and definitions are or will be adapted and checked by experts of risk communication and consumers for comprehensibility. E. g. instead of using the exact definition of EFSA for ADI (“The acceptable daily intake is an estimate of the amount of a substance in food or drinking water that can be consumed daily over a lifetime without presenting an appreciable risk to health. It is usually expressed as milligrams of the substance per kilogram of body weight and applies to chemical substances such as food additives, pesticide residues and veterinary drugs”) the ADI should be explained as “amount of a substance which a person can consume on a daily basis during one’s lifetime without an increased risk of getting ill” (Jansen et al., 2020a).

This implies also the use of terminology used by the public instead of terminology used by scientists. E. g. the word “intake” will be used instead of “exposure”. The current β -version does not include any definitions so far, but it is already decided and arranged that experts of risk communication from BfR will evaluate them before implementation.

- *Negative associations with specific words*

Words like “chemical” or “pesticide” evoke negative associations (Jansen, 2020a). However, lots of substances analysed in Total Diet Studies are chemicals and might be named accordingly in the short description of each substance. As no chemicals are included in TDS-Exposure, this will be an issue to discuss when respective data from BfR MEAL study will be included. However, beside the word “chemical” text segments will be checked for other words that might evoke negative associations.

- *Phrasing: explicit mentioning of specific characteristics of substances can be understood as the substance is a hazard (“because if not, it would not be mentioned”)*

Every text sections will be evaluated for irrelevant information that might lead to misunderstandings. This refers specifically to the short descriptions of substances.

- *Vague, ambiguous language: may lead to misinterpretations*

Several words in the context of food risk communication are mentioned by Jansen et al., (2020a) as words with ambiguous meaning. In particular this refers to words “risk”, “toxic” and “hazard”. Therefore this words are avoided in the current App-version.

Objectives

With regard to the objective of FNS-Cloud project, the current version of the app proves that content data from TDS can be organized in mobile apps and therefore be made available for consumers and other low-end users in this way.

Risk communication experts are involved in designing the app to make the data understandable and useful. An extensive evaluation/ survey whether the App meets the needs of different user groups (consumers, risk managers, other low-end users) is not objective of FNS-Cloud and needs to be done by the data providers considering the specifics of e.g. the national data as well as risk perception that differs also much between European countries. Further the user group that should be addressed for their national TDS data needs to be considered. Those evaluations are not in the scope and behind the possibilities of FNS-Cloud. However, also consumers, risk communication experts as well as other professional low-end users will be involved in usability testing to point out some possible issues to be described and considered when providing national TDS data using the app.

In conclusion, a concept for the app is developed considering possible issues that come with the purpose of a communication of scientific results addressed to consumers by involving risk communication experts in the development and selected consumers in the usability tests. The technical implementation has been tested. Several feedback-rounds are needed in order to improve the app and will be part of Deliverable 5.9.

5 Discussion and next steps

5.1 Preparing MCRA demonstrators

The MCRA use cases have successfully led to the combination of concentration data from TDS or monitoring programmes, consumption data, hazard characterisation data using advanced probabilistic assessment methods to characterise the risk of exposure to various substances (selected metals, pesticides) from food.

The use cases have also led to several points that might need further attention in future research:

1. Data are often organised ad-hoc in preparation of an analysis for a specific report or publication. Such data are often not FAIR, which restricts the possibilities for use in a wider community.
2. In this work, data were transferred directly from the project partner acting as test end user in FNS-Cloud (BfR, UGent, RIVM) to the partner that was developing the implementation in MCRA (WUR). In a future setup, such data could be made available in FNS Cloud infrastructures, where they could be accessed by Web APIs.
3. It is often difficult to combine datasets because different coding systems have been used for e.g. substances or foods. Code conversion is then necessary, but this conversion itself should also be transparent, and part of the FAIRified procedure.
4. There is often an interest in characterising risk for different sub-populations that are stratified by e.g. age groups, locations (e.g. countries or regions within a country), time periods (e.g. years or seasons) or other individual characteristics (e.g. breastfeeding individuals). Some of these characteristics relate to individuals in the human population. However, characteristic related to space and time are of a more general nature, and it may be relevant to apply selections not only to the consumption data, but also to the concentration data. This might be a reason for more structured modelling in the software tool.
5. There is often an interest in characterising risk for multiple populations or sub-populations in one assessment and summarising the results. This would be a useful extension of the functionality of the software.
6. Varying practices are used to handle censored concentrations in practical assessments. At BfR an approach is used where censored values reported as 'below LOD' are replaced by 0, and values reported as 'between LOD and LOQ' are replaced by LOD (modified lower bound or mLb approach). Currently, MCRA can handle only one type of censoring limit (which is then termed the limit of reporting, LOR), and extension of functionality may be useful to incorporate approaches based on the two censoring limits LOD and LOQ which might be available from concentration data.
7. Varying practices are in use to handle consumption data of individuals that have only one day in the consumption survey. One approach, used in the nickel case study, is to omit such individuals from the assessment. It may be useful to add functionality in MCRA to do this automatically.
8. MCRA can handle food hierarchies (e.g. individual foods as part of food groups) and use these in the results to present results at different levels of a hierarchy. However, hierarchies cannot yet be used for selection purposes in the front-end. This might be a useful functionality to add.
9. In practice, replicate concentration measurements are usually made per sample. For example, in the BfR TDS study up to eight MeHg measurements per sample are available. Currently, MCRA allows only one value per sample/substance combination. In the current approach, the mean of all quantified values was calculated in the conversion script. However, this ignores potential censored values. It might be useful to add functionality in MCRA to allow imputation of censored values at the single measurement level.
10. The use cases have shown that assessments can be very complicated due to the large number of datasets and settings that have to be organised or set. It will be of interest to develop standard actions where most of the data are pre-selected and most of the settings are pre-defined. This will make advanced risk assessment methods more accessible to end users such as risk assessors. In the further development of the standard actions, prospective users should have the opportunity to include their own more specific data if desired. For example, more recent or more specific occurrence data may be available. As another example, it is known that the collection of processing factors in the EFSA collection is still limited, and users may want to use their own version of a processing factor database.

The use cases with MCRA reported in section 3 of this report will be finalised and reported in a follow-up report (Deliverable 4.4). They are intended to be developed as demonstrators showing the possibility to use the already existing web-based application MCRA as an e-service to assess the exposure to and risk of chemicals in food. In preparation of these demonstrators a scheme has been set up to illustrate the intended set-up and use of the MCRA demonstrators (see Figure 5.1, copied from Deliverable 5.1).

Figure 5.1. Scheme for MCRA demonstrators.

5.2 Preparing the consumer app demonstrator

In the consumer app use case, the concept for providing TDS datasets in mobile apps designed for small screens was successfully developed and technical implementation tested. Still, before the app is “ready-to-use”, improvements and further developments have to be performed.

The current (β) version of the app works for smaller TDS-datasets like the dataset of the German Pilot TDS. With regard to the implementation of full-scale TDS, several points need to be considered in the further process:

- 1) Results of full-scale TDS (e. g. BfR MEAL study) are much more complex with regard to the number of analysed substances. In the current version, it was possible to present content data of all analysed substances in one graph (max. 6 are possible to show in one graph of small screens). Therefore, it needs to be considered how the concept can be adapted to present more or less 100 substances analysed, e. g. by grouping the substances.
- 2) Food categories as basis for comparisons of content data were defined for TDS-Exposure. It needs to be considered whether an adaption is necessary for other TDS.
- 3) In TDS-Exposure, only the consumption survey for adults (NVSII) were considered. Therefore, all results and statements regard to adults. BfR MEAL study also considers children, an adaption of the concept will be necessary in some parts.
- 4) Possible risk communication-related issues need to be focused. Therefore, every adaption or improvement of the concept needs to be evaluated by experts of risk communication.

- 5) Current language of the app is English. In terms of understandability (in particular with regard to German speaking users), the app needs to be translated in German (or other languages, depending on implemented TDS). Still, the use of the app in English needs to stay an option.

In addition to concept-related improvements, several tests rounds need to be conducted in order to evaluate the usability, understandability and possible risk communication-related issues:

- 1) Periodic feedback round with experts of risk communication

Feedback rounds with colleagues from the risk communication department of BfR are already conducted in the development process of the Use Case and will be continued in Demonstrators. Objective of these test rounds are the periodic evaluation of the concept and performed implementations in order to prevent time-consuming improvements afterwards. Also, the app and, in particular, embedded information (explanations, disclaimers, substance descriptions) are and will be evaluated under aspects of risk communications.

- 2) Usability test with colleagues from BfR

To test the usability with focus on technical aspects, tests will be conducted with colleagues from BfR.

- 3) Tests with low-end users

Finally, testing of the app is being planned with low-end users. Since initially only content data of German TDS are included in the app, usability tests will be conducted with selected consumers and other low-end users (potential professional users that are not experts for TDS concept or exposure assessment). Objective of these tests are to see the usability and comprehensibility of the app for potential users without expert knowledge regarding exposure assessment and TDS. Also risk communication experts will be involved in the testing to give their view what opportunities and concerns are seen in the use of the app in risk communication.

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7 Appendices

7.1 Data formats

7.1.1 Data formats MCRA

This section describes the current data formats of MCRA for consumption data, concentration data, and TDS food composition data. This is a selection of all the data formats of MCRA and does not include detailed descriptions. For more details, see: <https://mcra.rivm.nl/Documentation>.

7.1.1.1 Populations catalogues

In MCRA, the population that is the object of exposure or risk assessments is a primary entity. Like all main entities in MCRA it should be identified in table Populations with a unique identifier, and optionally with a name (if not specified, the id is used as name), and a description.

The individuals within a populations can be further characterised in table PopulationIndividualPropertyValues with properties defined in table IndividualProperties, either at the individual level (e.g. age, gender, region, breastfeeding, etc.) or the individual-day level (e.g. period, season, month).

7.1.1.1.1 MCRA table Populations

Name	Type	Description	Required
idPopulation	AlphaNumeric(50)	Unique identification code of the population.	Yes
Name	AlphaNumeric(100)	The name of the population.	No
Description	AlphaNumeric(200)	Description of of the population.	No

7.1.1.1.2 MCRA table IndividualProperties

Name	Type	Description	Required
idIndividualProperty	AlphaNumeric(50)	The code of the property.	Yes
Name	AlphaNumeric(100)	The name of the property.	No
PropertyLevel	PropertyLevelTypes	The level of the property. This type follows a controlled terminology, with possible values: Individual or IndividualDay.	No
Description	AlphaNumeric(200)	Description of the property.	No
Type	IndividualPropertyTypes	This field specifies the type of the values of this individual property. This type follows a controlled terminology, with possible values: Boolean, Categorical (default), Numeric, Nonnegative, Integer, NonnegativeInteger, Month, Datetime, Gender.	No

7.1.1.1.3 MCRA table PopulationIndividualPropertyValues

Name	Type	Description	Required
idPopulation	AlphaNumeric(50)	The code of the population to which the property is attached. The provided population code should match with a code of the populations table.	Yes
idIndividualProperty	AlphaNumeric(50)	The name or reference of the individual property.	Yes
Value	AlphaNumeric(50)	The value of the property.	No
MinValue	Numeric	Minimum value of the value of the property.	No
MaxValue	Numeric	Maximum value of the value of the property.	No
StartDate	DateTime	Starting date of the specific time window marking this population.	No
EndDate	DateTime	End date of the specific time window marking this population.	No

7.1.1.2 Foods catalogues

In MCRA, foods should be described in a table Foods with a unique identification code, and optionally with a name (if not specified, the id is used as name) and a description. Foods include foods-as-eaten (i.e. foods specified in consumption data), TDS foods (i.e. food mixtures as investigated in total diet studies) and modelled foods (i.e. the foods that are measured in monitoring programs and which will appear in the output).

Note that MCRA does not include a separate catalogue for storing TDS foods definitions. Instead, in MCRA, these are viewed as foods. Hence, definitions of TDS foods should be provided in the foods catalogue.

Foods can be ordered in hierarchies by using a table FoodHierarchies. Such hierarchies on modelled foods are visible in some MCRA outputs.

Foods can be processed, and food processing types can be defined in a table FoodProcessingTypes. Codes for foods and food processing types define implicitly new codes for processed foods, using a hyphen ('-') as separator. Example: idFood 'Apple' and idProcessingType 'Peeling' define a code 'Apple-Peeling' for peeled apple.

7.1.1.2.1 MCRA table Foods

Name	Type	Description	Required
idFood	AlphaNumeric (50)	The unique identification code of the food.	Yes
Name	AlphaNumeric (100)	The name of the food.	No
Description	AlphaNumeric (200)	Food description.	No

7.1.1.2.2 MCRA table FoodHierarchies

Name	Type	Description	Required
idFood	AlphaNumeric (50)	Food code of the food.	Yes
idParent	AlphaNumeric (50)	Food code of the parent food.	Yes

7.1.1.2.3 MCRA table ProcessingTypes

Name	Type	Description	Required
idProcessingType	AlphaNumeric(50)	The unique identification code of the processing type.	Yes
Name	AlphaNumeric(100)	The processing name.	No
Description	AlphaNumeric(200)	The processing type description.	No
DistributionType	AlphaNumeric	The distribution type. Simulated processing factors are restricted to the interval (0,1) using a logistic-normal distribution (= 1) or simulated processing factors are restricted to positive values using a log-normal distribution (= 2).	Yes
BulkingBlending	Boolean	For types of processing applied on large batches e.g. juicing, sauce/puree. No bulking/blending = 0, bulking blending = 1.	Yes

7.1.1.3 Substances catalogue

MCRA requires a catalogue of substance definitions. This is a table in which all substances relevant for exposure assessment are specified in terms of an identification code, a name (optional) and a description (optional). Also additional properties may be specified, but these are not relevant for the current discussion.

7.1.1.3.1 MCRA table Substances

Name	Type	Description	Aliases	Required
idSubstance	AlphaNumeric(50)	The unique identification code of the substance. This code may be from an existing coding system, such as CAS-codes or Param codes of EFSA, or it may be a used-defined code.	idSubstance, SubstanceId, Substance, Code, Id, idCompound, CompoundId, Compound	Yes
Name	AlphaNumeric(100)	The substance name.	Name, CompoundName, SubstanceName, PesticideName	No
Description	AlphaNumeric(200)	Substance description.	Description	No

7.1.1.4 Consumption data

Consumption data is described using three main tables: a table of food survey definitions, a table containing the individuals linked to the food survey definitions, and a consumptions table specifying the consumptions of the individuals of the survey.

7.1.1.4.1 MCRA table FoodSurveys

Name	Type	Description	Required
idSurvey	AlphaNumeric(50)	Unique identification code of the food consumption survey.	Yes
Description	AlphaNumeric(200)	Description of the food consumption survey.	No
Location	AlphaNumeric(50)	The location or country where survey is held. It is recommended to use ISO Alpha-2 country codes.	No
BodyWeightUnit	BodyWeightUnits	The unit of bodyweight of the individuals of the survey: kg (default) or g.	No
AgeUnit	AgeUnit	The unit of age, i.e., year or month.	No
ConsumptionUnit	ConsumptionUnits	The unit of the use/consumption amounts of the consumptions of the survey: g (default) or kg or CustomUnit (see table food consumption quantifications table).	No
StartDate	DateTime	The start date of the survey.	No
EndDate	DateTime	The end date of the survey.	No
NumberOfSurveyDays	Integer	The number of days each individual participated in the survey.	Yes
idPopulation	AlphaNumeric(50)	Unique identification code of the population.	No

7.1.1.4.2 MCRA table Individuals

Name	Type	Description	Required
idIndividual	AlphaNumeric(50)	Unique identification code of the individual.	Yes
idFoodSurvey	AlphaNumeric(50)	The identification code / short name of survey.	Yes
BodyWeight	Numeric	The body weight of the individual.	Yes
SamplingWeight	Numeric	The sampling weight for an individual (default = 1).	No
NumberOfSurveyDays	Integer	The number of days the individual participated in the survey.	No
Age	Numeric	The age of the individual.	No

Gender	AlphaNumeric(50)	The gender of the individual. It is recommended to use the codes Male/Female for coding the gender.	No
Other individual properties		Other individual properties can be added just like the fields age and gender. These properties are automatically parsed as co-factors or co-variables.	No

7.1.1.4.3 MCRA table FoodConsumptions

Name	Type	Description	Required
idIndividual	AlphaNumeric(50)	The unique identification code of the consumer (individual).	Yes
idFood	AlphaNumeric(50)	The food code (food as eaten code).	Yes
idUnit	AlphaNumeric(50)	Identification code of the unit in which the food is consumed (e.g. plate, cup, spoon).	No
idDay	AlphaNumeric(50)	Identification code of the day of consumption, sequential number	Yes
idMeal	AlphaNumeric(50)	Identification code of the meal (eating occasion within a day).	No
Amount	Numeric	The consumed portion of food in g (default) or kg or quantity of a plate, cup, spoon. Days without consumptions are not recorded.	Yes
DateConsumed	DateTime	The date of the consumption.	No

7.1.1.5 Concentration data

MCRA supports input of occurrence/concentration data in several formats, among which is the EFSA SSD format. Internally, MCRA works with a relational table schema composed of a samples table, defining the samples of the concentration data, a sample analyses table describing the analyses performed on the food samples, an analytical methods and analytical method substances table describing the analytical methods used by the sample analyses, and a concentrations table in which the concentration values of the sample analyses are recorded. When uploading SSD data, MCRA will internally convert the data to this format.

7.1.1.5.1 MCRA table ConcentrationsSSD

Column name	Key	Required	Type	Size	Description
labSampCode	Primary	Yes	AlphaNumeric	25	Code of the laboratory sample. MCRA will use the combination of labSampCode and labSubSampCode as unique code for a sample.
labSubSampCode	Primary	No	AlphaNumeric	4	Code of the laboratory sub-sample. MCRA will use the combination of labSampCode and labSubSampCode as unique code for a sample.
sampCountry		Yes	AlphaNumeric	2	Two-letter code to identify the country of sampling.

prodCode		Yes	AlphaNumeric	20	Code identifying the food as measured. Should be equal to a code idFood in the Foods table.
sampY		Yes	Integer	4	Year of sampling.
sampM		No	Integer	2	Month of sampling.
sampD		No	Integer	2	Day of sampling.
analysisY	Primary	Yes	Integer	4	Year of analysis.
analysisM		No	Integer	2	Month of analysis.
analysisD		No	Integer	2	Day of analysis.
paramCode		Yes	AlphaNumeric	20	Code identifying the substance.
resUnit		Yes	AlphaNumeric	5	Unit of residue measurement.
resLOD		No	Numeric		Residue Limit Of Detection. Required if resType is LOD. MCRA will use resLOD as LOR if resLOQ is not provided.
resLOQ		No	Numeric		Residue Limit Of Quantification. Required if resType is LOQ MCRA will use resLOQ as LOR if provided.
resVal		No	Numeric		Required if resType is VAL.
resType		Yes	AlphaNumeric	3	Type of residue data. Should be VAL, LOQ or LOD.

7.1.1.5.2 MCRA table FoodSamples

Name	Type	Description	Required
idFoodSample	AlphaNumeric(50)	The identification number of the food sample.	Yes
idFood	AlphaNumeric(50)	The food code.	Yes
Location	AlphaNumeric(50)	The location or country code, sampling location.	No
DateSampling	DateTime	The date of sampling.	No

7.1.1.5.3 MCRA table SampleAnalyses

Name	Type	Description	Required
idAnalysisSample	AlphaNumeric(50)	The identification number of the analysed sample.	Yes
idFoodSample	AlphaNumeric(50)	The identification number of the food sample.	Yes
idAnalyticalMethod	AlphaNumeric(50)	The code of method of analysis.	Yes
DateAnalysis	DateTime	The date of the analysis.	No

7.1.1.5.4 MCRA table AnalyticalMethods

Name	Type	Description	Required
idAnalyticalMethod	AlphaNumeric(50)	The code for the method of analysis.	Yes

Description	AlphaNumeric(200)	Additional description of method of analysis.	No
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7.1.1.5.5 MCRA table AnalyticalMethodSubstances

Name	Type	Description	Required
idAnalyticalMethod	AlphaNumeric(50)	The code of method of analysis.	Yes
idSubstance	AlphaNumeric(50)	The substance code.	Yes
LOR	Numeric	The limit of reporting (LOR). In MCRA, LOR just means the limit below which no quantitative result has been reported. Depending on a laboratory's format of reporting, LOR may be a limit of detection (LOD), a limit of quantification (LOQ) or another limit.	Yes
ConcentrationUnit	ConcentrationUnits	The unit of the concentrations/LORs reported by the analytical method for this substance (default mg/kg).	No

7.1.1.5.6 MCRA table SampleConcentrations

Name	Type	Description	Required
idAnalysisSample	AlphaNumeric(50)	The identification number of the analysed sample.	Yes
idSubstance	AlphaNumeric(50)	The substance code.	Yes
Concentration	Numeric	The measured concentration.	Yes

7.1.1.6 Processing factors

Processing factors are multiplication factors to derive the concentration in a processed food from the concentration in an unprocessed food and can be specified for identified processing types (e.g., cooking, washing, drying). Processing factors are primarily used in dietary exposure assessments to correct for the effect of processing on substance concentrations in dietary exposure calculations. In MCRA, processing factors connect two food codes, one for the processed food and one for the unprocessed food. The preferred scheme is to specify only the code of the unprocessed food and the processing type (facet), the code of the processed food is defined by the other two, with a hyphen ('-') as separator. For reasons of backward compatibility, the code of the processed food (so preferably idFood-idProcessingType) should still be specified.

Processing factors are defined for triplets of processing type, food, and (optionally) substance. If substance is not specified the processing factor applies to all substances in the assessment. The processing types are defined in the processing types table and the processing factors are defined in the processing factors table.

7.1.1.6.1 MCRA table ProcessingFactors

Name	Type	Description	Required
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idProcessingType	AlphaNumeric(50)	The code of the processing type.	Yes
idSubstance	AlphaNumeric(50)	The code of the substance.	No
idFoodProcessed	AlphaNumeric(50)	The code of the processed food.	Yes
idFoodUnprocessed	AlphaNumeric(50)	The code of the unprocessed food.	Yes
Nominal	Numeric	The nominal value (best estimate of 50th percentile) of processing factor (defines median processing factor).	No

7.1.1.7 TDS food sample compositions

In MCRA, the compositions of TDS samples are described in the TDS food sample compositions table. Here, a composite sample/composite food is identified as a food, and referenced with an “idTDSFood” and the food included in the sample is identified with “idFood” with a certain pooled amount. Multiple foods can be included in the same TDS sample by adding multiple records.

Note: this current data format may not prove to be ideal. It may be better to split this table into two tables: one defining the TDS samples (including regionality and seasonality, and perhaps some other properties) and a separate table for the compositions (foods in the TDS sample with their amounts).

7.1.1.7.1 Table TDSSampleCompositions

Name	Type	Description	Required
idTDSFood	AlphaNumeric(50)	The code of the TDS food.	Yes
idFood	AlphaNumeric(50)	Sub-food of the TDS food.	Yes
PooledAmount	Numeric	Total weight (in g) or volume (in ml) of the food.	Yes
Description	AlphaNumeric(200)	Additional description of the TDS sample (e.g. number of subsamples).	No
Regionality	AlphaNumeric	Regionality information.	No
Seasonality	AlphaNumeric	Seasonality information.	No

7.1.2 Data formats BfR

7.1.2.1 Consumption data: VELs data format

7.1.2.1.1 VELs table Individual consumptions

Column name	Translation	Description	Relevance for Exposure Assessment

Proband	Individual	The unique identification code of the consumer (individual).	yes
Protokolltag	Reporting day	Identification code of the day of consumption, sequential Number. Should be N=6 for each individual (CAVE: some individuals did not complete 6 full days; see Table 4).	yes
sbls	[German food coding system]	The food code (food as eaten code)	yes
menge_tag	amount_day	The consumed portion size of food in g	yes

7.1.2.1.2 VELs table Individual breast-feeding

Column name	Translation	Description	Relevance for Exposure Assessment
Proband	Individual	The unique identification code of the consumer (individual).	yes
Stillen	breastfeeding	Identification code if child is breastfed (stillen > 0 means breastfed)	yes

7.1.2.1.3 VELs table Individual characteristics

Column name	Translation	Description	Relevance for Exposure Assessment
Persid	Individuals ID	Not required as "proband" is unique identifier	no
Nummer	Individuals ID (other)	Not required as "proband" is unique identifier	no
Standort	Location*	Name of residence of the individual	yes (in case of regional evaluations)
Ostdeut	East Germany	Not relevant	no
datum1	Date 1*	First day of first reporting period	yes
datum2	Date 2*	Second day of first reporting period	yes
datum3	Date 3*	Third day of first reporting period	yes
besonder	Specific characteristics	E.g. allergies, chronic diseases; first reporting period	no
krank1	ill 1	Information about illness on first day in first reporting period	no
krank2	ill 2	Information about illness on second day in first reporting period	no

krank3	ill 3	Information about illness on third day in first reporting period	no
gebdatum	Birthday	Date of birth	yes
geschl	gender	Differentiation between male and female	yes
größe	height	Height of individual (cm) measured in first reporting period	no
gewicht	Body weight	Body weight of individual (kg) measured in first reporting period Note: body weight of the first reporting period (Date of first reporting date) will be used for exposure assessment. In case of missing values (use body weight of "gewichtb")	yes
datum1b	Date 1b**	First day of second reporting period	yes
datum2b	Date 2b**	Second day of second reporting period	yes
datum3b	Date 3b**	Third day of second reporting period	yes
besond_b	Specific characteristics	E.g. allergies, chronic diseases; second reporting period	no
krank1b	ill 1b	Information about illness on first day in first second period	no
krank2b	ill 2b	Information about illness on second day in second reporting period	no
krank3b	ill 3b	Information about illness on first day in second reporting period	no
größeb	heightb	Height of individual (cm) measured in second reporting period	no
gewichtb	Body weight b	Body weight of individual (kg) measured in second reporting period CAVE: missing values (use body weight of "gewicht")	yes
bemerk	remark	Field for remarks	no
alt_grup	age_group	Identification code for pre-defined age groups	no
proband	Individual	The unique identification code of the consumer (individual).	yes

* In case of regional evaluations individuals need to be grouped as follows according to the BfR MEAL sampling regions:

- Recode:
 'Standort': (0=3) (2=4) (3=1) (4=3) (5=3) (6=1) (7=3) (8=2) (9=2)
- Label:
 1 "Region Ost"

- 2 "Region Süd"
- 3 "Region West"
- 4 "Region Nord".

**For the use case consumption days (date 1 - 3 and date 1b - 3b) will be matched to the above defined sampling seasons (Summer season: April-September; Winter season: October – March)

7.1.2.1.4 VELS table Individual survey days

Column name	Translation	Description	Relevance for Exposure Assessment
proband	Individual	The unique identification code of the consumer (individual).	yes
anz_bls_tag	not relevant	not relevant	no
anz_protokoll_tage	Amount_reporting_days	Amount of reporting days per individual. Note: Consumption needs to be weighted according to reported days.	yes

7.1.2.2 Concentration data : BfR MEAL data format

7.1.2.2.1 BfR MEAL table Results report

Column name	Translation	Description	Relevance for Exposure Assessment
Probencode (Auftraggeber)	Sample Code (BfR)	The unique identification code of the sample (Sample Analysis Code). Includes information about the food (pool) rationality, seasonality, organic/conventional production	yes
Probenbezeichnung	Sample name	Name of food pool (composite sample)	yes
Datum Probenübergabe	Date of sample transfer	Indicates the date the sample was transferred to the laboratory	no
Probencode (Auftragnehmer)	Sample code (laboratory)	The unique identification code of the sample in the contracted lab.	no
Analyt	Analyte	Indicates the analysed substance	yes
Interner Standard	Internal standard	Internal standard used for analysis	no
LOD	LOD	Limit of detection	no
LOQ	LOQ	Limit of quantification	no
Einheit LOD/ LOQ	Unit LOD / LOQ	Indicates unit of the reporting limits	yes
Datum Analyse	Date of analysis	Date when food pool was analysed	no
Ergebnis 1	Result 1	Result of first analysis (without dilution factor). Field can be a number, a point "." or be empty.	no

		Number: quantified result above LOQ Point ".": value <LOD/LOQ Empty: no analysis (Analysis can contain from one, up to eight results. Fields can be empty in case of less than eight analyses.)	
Value Type	Value Type	<LOD = Result is below LOD <LOQ = Results is below LOQ res = quantified result Empty: no analysis	no
Ergebnis 2	Result 2	see above	no
Value Type	Value Type	see above	no
Ergebnis 3	Result 3	see above	no
Value Type	Value Type	see above	no
Ergebnis 4	Result 4	see above	no
Value Type	Value Type	see above	no
Ergebnis 5	Result 5	see above	no
Value Type	Value Type	see above	no
Ergebnis 6	Result 6	see above	no
Value Type	Value Type	see above	no
Ergebnis 7	Result 7	see above	no
Value Type	Value Type	see above	no
Ergebnis 8	Result 8	see above	no
Value Type	Value Type	see above	no
Verdünnungsfaktor (VF) (1=unverdünnt)	Dilution factor (DF) (1 = not diluted)	Indicates if, and how much water was added during homogenisation. Sometimes the laboratory already considered dilution in their analysis. Then the DF is in each field "1".	no
effektiver LOD	applicable LOD	Considers dilution in case the lab did not already consider it.	yes
effektiver LOD	applicable LOQ	Considers dilution in case it was not already considered by the lab	yes

Ergebnis 1 + VF	Result 1 + DF	<p>Result of first analysis (including dilution factor). Field can be a number, a point "." or be empty.</p> <p>Number: quantified result above LOQ</p> <p>Point ".": value below LOD/LOQ</p> <p>Empty: no analysis (Analysis can contain from one, up to five results. Fields can be empty in case of less than five analyses).</p>	yes
Value Type 1	Value Type 1	<p><LOD = Result is below LOD</p> <p><LOQ = Result is below LOQ</p> <p>res = quantified result</p> <p>Empty: no analysis</p>	yes
Ergebnis 2 + VF	Result 2 + DF	see above	yes
Value Type 2	Value Type 2	see above	yes
Ergebnis 3 + VF	Result 3 + DF	see above	yes
Value Type 3	Value Type 3	see above	yes
Ergebnis 4 + VF	Result 4 + DF	see above	yes
Value Type 4	Value Type 4	see above	yes
Ergebnis 5 + VF	Result 5 + DF	see above	yes
Value Type 5	Value Type 5	see above	yes
Ergebnis 6 + VF	Result 6 + DF	see above	yes
Value Type 6	Value Type 6	see above	yes
Ergebnis 7 + VF	Result 7 + DF	see above	yes
Value Type 7	Value Type 7	see above	yes
Ergebnis 8 + VF	Result 8 + DF	see above	yes
Value Type 8	Value Type 8	see above	yes

7.1.2.3 TDS composition data: BfR MEAL format

7.1.2.3.1 BfR MEAL table Samples

Column name	Translation	Description	Relevance for Exposure Assessment
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MEAL-Code	MEAL code	The code for the food groups selected for the food list in MEAL (Food Code). Describes the foods.	yes
Sample Code	Sample Code	Code for pooled samples in MEAL. Unique for each pooled sample. Describes the foods including their stratification.	Yes
Probenbezeichnung	Sample name	Name of the sample (relates to the MEAL-Code); same as "Gr Bez" in the table "BfR table mapping")	no
Pooled Amount/Subsamples	Pooled Amount/Subsamples	Number of single food included in the pooled sample.	no

7.1.2.3.2 BfR MEAL table MEAL/VELS mapping

Column name	Translation	Description	Relevance for Exposure Assessment
sbls	[German food coding system]	The food code (food as eaten code).	yes
bezeichnung	Food name	Name of food in the consumption survey	yes
Gr Code	Group code	Groups consumed foods to pooled samples.	no
Gr Bez	Sample name	Name of the sample (relates to the MEAL-Code/Food Code)	yes
MEAL-Code	MEAL code	The code for the food groups selected for the food list in MEAL (Food Code). Describes the foods.	yes
HptGr Nr	No. of main food group	Numbers main food groups according to FoodEx2 classification	no
HptGr Code	Code. of main food group	Code of main food groups according to FoodEx2 classification	no
HptGr Bez	Name of main food group	Name of the related main food group according to FoodEx2 classification	no

7.1.3 Data formats UG

7.1.3.1.1 INNIBEL table Concentrations in EFSA format

Column name	Code	Translation	Description	Mandatory or Optional
sampMatCode	FoodEx2 Codes	Coded description of the matrix of the sample taken.	Samples in FoodEx2 were encoded according to the guidance for the harmonised use of the FoodEx2 system and the quality control of the codes (EFSA, 2015).	Mandatory
paramType	P001A	Type of parameter.	Individual: The reported analytical result refers to one single compound (Nickel).	Mandatory
paramCode	RF-00000182-CHE	Coded description of parameter.	Nickel (Ni)	Mandatory
resUnit	G050A	Result unit.	This element indicates the units of measurement for the numerical values resLOD, resLOQ, resVal, microgram/kilogram	Mandatory
resLOD		Result limit of detection.	The limit of detection (LOD) is the lowest concentration that can be determined to be statistically different from a 'blank' analytical result.	Optional

resLOQ		Result limit of quantification.	The resLOQ, the numerical value of the limit of quantification (LOQ), is the lowest validated residue concentration or mass of the analyte that has been validated with acceptable accuracy by applying the complete analytical method, which can be quantified and reported by routine monitoring with validated methods.	Dependent mandatory
resVal		Result value.	The resVal were used to report the measured residue concentration of the substance (Nickel) in the product expressed in the units reported in resUnit. resVal is mandatory if resType=VAL.	Optional
exprResType	B001A	Expression of result type.	Used to indicate when the concentration is expressed as a percentage of a component of the sample; for example, on a dry weight basis.	Optional
resType		Type of results	<p>The resType indicates the type of analytical result obtained for a substance in a product.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - VAL: The result were quantified at a validated level and resVal is reported. - LOQ: The residue was below the LOQ. - LOD: The residue was below the LOD and resLOD is reported. 	Mandatory

evalCode	J029A	Evaluation of the result.	<p>It contains codes linked to the RESEVAL catalogue. This element</p> <p>contains the final evaluation of the analysed parameter by the laboratory or risk manager. The residue was not evaluated as no limit applies to the substance or residue measured in the sample.</p>	Mandatory
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7.1.3.1.2 Table Consumptions BNFCs data 2014-2015 (UG selected subset of variables).

Variable	Translation	Description
Id		Individual identification code
INT_NUM	EPIC interview number	Day 1 or Day 2
agegroup	Age of participant	1= 3-9 years 2= 10-17 years 3= 18-64 years
wght	Body weight	Measured body weight in kg
Consumption (g/kg b.w)	Consumed quantity in grams per kg of the consumer's body weight	
FOODNUM	Code of Food, Recipe, Ingredient or Supplement	Range from 00001 to 02636

FoodEx2_code	Coding system established by EFSA	Including the main code as well as descriptors (facets)
NAME	Recipe or Food or Ingredient or supplement Name	

7.2 Data conversion

7.2.1 Conversion from BfR to MCRA formats

Automated conversion is done mostly for the larger consumption and concentration data tables, whereas most of the additional data/catalogue tables were created manually.

The conversion and creation of the MCRA datasets is performed offline, and produces the MCRA datasets that can be uploaded to the MCRA platform where they can be used for performing the TDS exposure assessments. The table below summarizes that MCRA data tables that we generated, and for each MCRA data table whether the mapping was done manually or automatic. The sections below describe the mapping procedures in more detail.

Dataset	MCRA Data type	Data table	Mapping method
Catalogues FNS Case Study MeHg DE Children	Populations	Populations	Manual creation.
		IndividualProperties	Manual creation.
		PopulationIndividualPropertyValues	Manual creation.
	Foods	Foods	Automatic creation using python scripts.
		FoodHierarchies	Manual creation.
	Substances	Substances	Manual creation.
	Effects	Effects	Manual creation.
	Hazard characterisations	HazardCharacterisations	Manual creation.
VELS Consumptions 2001-2002	Consumptions	Surveys	Automatic conversion using python scripts.

		Individuals	Automatic conversion using python scripts.
		IndividualDays	Automatic conversion using python scripts.
		Consumptions	Automatic conversion using python scripts.
Artificial MeHg Concentrations FNS Case Study	Concentrations	FoodSamples	Automatic conversion using python scripts.
		AnalyticalMethods	Automatic conversion using python scripts.
		AnalyticalMethodSubstances	Automatic conversion using python scripts.
		SampleAnalyses	Automatic conversion using python scripts.
		SampleConcentrations	Automatic conversion using python scripts.
	TDS sample compositions	TdsFoodSampleCompositions	Automatic conversion using python scripts.

7.2.1.1 Case study catalogues

7.2.1.1.1 MCRA Populations, individual properties, and population individual properties tables

An MCRA populations catalogue is created manually, containing the definitions of the population targetted by the VELs study and also the various sub-populations that are targetted in the various scenarios. This populations catalogue contains three tables; one defining the populations in general, and two for defining and describing the specific individual properties of the individuals of the populations.

7.2.1.1.2 MCRA Foods table

Two food coding systems are used: the food coding system of the VELs consumption data and the coding system of the composite samples/TDS foods as used in the MEAL concentration data. Note that MCRA regards the TDS composite samples as a special type of food. The code/name tuples of these two food coding systems are combined to form the MCRA foods table. For filling this table, the food codes and names are automatically extracted from the available original data files.

7.2.1.1.3 MCRA Food hierarchies table

For the MEAL coding system, which is a hierarchical coding system, also the codes of the food groups are included. The food-hierarchy of the MEAL coding system was included by adding an MCRA food hierarchies table containing the parent/child code tuples.

7.2.1.1.4 MCRA Substances table

No explicit coding system is used in the MEAL concentration data, only the substance name is provided. For the case study dataset, containing only methylmercury, it is decided to align with the EFSA PARAM coding system. A simple MCRA substances catalogue is created containing a single record for methylmercury with its EFSA PARAM code RF-00000169-CHE as identifier.

7.2.1.1.5 MCRA Effects and hazard characterisations

A hazard characterisations table containing the reference dose of methylmercury was created manually based a TWI for methylmercury of 1.3 µg/kg b.w. established by EFSA (2012). The associated effect is Kidney damage, for which an effect definition was also created manually in the effects table.

7.2.1.2 Consumption data

The MCRA consumption data is extracted from the VELs consumption data tables. The tables below illustrate how the VELs table fields map to the MCRA consumption data tables. In the sections below, a description will be provided for each MCRA table on how this table is created.

Table 3 Mapping VELs individuals table fields to the MCRA data format.

Column name	Translation	Relevance for Exposure Assessment	MCRA table name	MCRA field name
persid	Individuals ID	no (Not required as "proband" is unique identifier)	-	-
nummer	Individuals ID (other)	no	-	-
standort	Location	yes (in case of regional evaluations)	Individuals	Region [generic individual property]
ostdeut	East Germany	no	-	-
datum1	Date 1	yes	Consumptions	Date consumed
datum2	Date 2	yes	Consumptions	Date consumed
datum3	Date 3	yes	Consumptions	Date consumed
besonder	Specific characteristics	no	-	-
krank1	ill 1	no	-	-
krank2	ill 2	no	-	-
krank3	ill 3	no	-	-
gebdatum	Birthday	yes	Individuals	Age [extracted from datum1 and gebdatum]
geschl	gender	yes	Individuals	Gender
größe	height	no	Individuals	Height [generic individual property]
gewicht	Body weight	yes	Individuals	BodyWeight
datum1b	Date 1b	yes	Consumptions	Date consumed
datum2b	Date 2b	yes	Consumptions	Date consumed
datum3b	Date 3b	yes	Consumptions	Date consumed
besond_b	Specific characteristics	no	-	-

krank1b	ill 1b	no	-	-
krank2b	ill 2b	no	-	-
krank3b	ill 3b	no	-	-
größeb	heightb	yes	Individuals	Height [generic individual property]
gewichtb	Body weight b	yes	Individuals	BodyWeight [can be used if bodyweight from first period is missing]
bemerk	remark	no	-	-
alt_grup	age_group	no	-	-
proband	Individual	yes	Individuals	idIndividual

Mapping BfR table reporting days

Column name	Translation	Relevance for Exposure Assessment	MCRA table	MCRA field name
proband	Individual	Yes	Individuals	idIndividual
anz_bls_tag	not relevant	No		-
anz_protokoll_t age	Amount_reporting_days	yes	Individuals	NumberOfSurveyDays

Mapping BfR table breast feeding information

Column name	Translation	Relevance for Exposure Assessment		MCRA field name
Proband	Individual	yes	Individuals	idIndividual
Stillen	breastfeeding	yes	<i>Individuals</i>	Breastfeeding [generic individual property]

7.2.1.2.1 MCRA food survey table

MCRA requires a specification of food surveys and a reference to the food survey, which the individual was part of through the field idFoodSurvey. Since the present data is solely about one food survey, being the VELs study, this survey definition is created manually from the metadata, and idFoodSurvey should point to this record. This table further requires start and end dates of the survey, for which the interval was set from 1-1-2001 to 31-12-2002.

7.2.1.2.2 MCRA individuals table

The VELs individuals table is the main table for constructing the MCRA individuals table. Each record in the VELs individuals table (marked as relevant for exposure assessment) maps to one record in the MCRA individuals table. In MCRA, the number of days that an individual actually participated in the survey is stored at the individual level, in the individuals table, not in the consumptions table. The number of reporting days from the VELs reporting days table therefore maps to the number of individual days field of the individuals table of MCRA. The information of the region of the individual and on whether the individual was breast feeding during the survey period is added as additional individual column in the MCRA individuals table.

7.2.1.2.3 MCRA food consumptions table

The BfR individual consumptions table maps one-to-one to the MCRA consumptions table, with column mappings described below.

Mapping BfR individual consumptions

Column name	Translation	Relevance for Exposure Assessment	MCRA table name	MCRA field name
Proband	Individual	yes	Consumptions	idIndividual
Protokolltag	Reporting day	yes	Consumptions	idDay
sbls	[German food coding system]	yes	Consumptions	idFood
menge_tag	amount_day	yes	Consumptions	Amount

7.2.1.2.4 MCRA individual days table

An MCRA individual days table is extracted from the VELs individuals and reporting days tables. For each individual the dates of the six survey days (two periods of three days) are recorded. An individual day record is created for each field for which this date is specified, including the date as survey date.

7.2.1.3 Concentration data

The MCRA concentration data tables are extracted from the MEAL reporting table. In this conversion, the substance is coded using the EFSA PARAM coding system. The table below describes how the various field types map to the different MCRA relational concentration data tables. In the sections below, the creation procedure for each MCRA data table is provided.

In the MEAL concentration data, up to 8 measurements per sample are reported. MCRA requires a single value per sample. If there is at least one quantified value, the mean of the quantified values is taken and used in the MCRA SampleConcentrations data. Nondetects (points) and missing values (empty cells) in the BfR data are then ignored. If there are no quantified values no record is included in the MCRA SampleConcentrations data. However, the sample is included in the Sample data, and the LOQ is used as LOR in the AnalyticalMethodsSubstance table. The sample is then associated with a '< LOQ' result.

Mapping BfR table concentrations

Column name	Translation	Relevance for Exposure Assessment	MCRA table name	MCRA field name
Probencode (Auftraggeber)	Sample Code (BfR)	yes	Food samples / Sample analyses	idFoodSample / idAnalysisSample
Probenbezeichnung	Sample name	yes	-	-
Datum Probenübergabe	Date of sample transfer	no	-	-
Probencode (Auftragnehmer)	Sample code (laboratory)	no	-	-
Analyt	Analyte	yes	Analytical method substances	Recorded to PARAM Code to become the idSubstance

Interner Standard	Internal standard	no	-	-
LOD	LOD	no	-	-
LOQ	LOQ	no	-	-
Einheit LOD/ LOQ	Unit LOD / LOQ	yes	Analytical method substances	ConcentrationUnit
Datum Analyse	Date of analysis	no	Sample analyses	DateAnalysis
Ergebnis 1	Result 1	no	-	-
Value Type	Value Type	no	-	-
Ergebnis 2	Result 2	no	-	-
Value Type	Value Type	no	-	-
Ergebnis 3	Result 3	no	-	-
Value Type	Value Type	no	-	-
Ergebnis 4	Result 4	no	-	-
Value Type	Value Type	no	-	-
Ergebnis 5	Result 5	no	-	-
Value Type	Value Type	no	-	-
Ergebnis 6	Result 6	no	-	-
Value Type	Value Type	no	-	-
Ergebnis 7	Result 7	no	-	-
Value Type	Value Type	no	-	-
Ergebnis 8	Result 8	no	-	-
Value Type	Value Type	no	-	-
Verdünnungsfaktor (VF) (1=unverdünnt)	Dilution factor (DF) (1 = not diluted)	no	-	-
effektiver LOD	applicable LOD	yes		
effektiver LOQ	applicable LOQ	yes	Analytical method substances	LOR
Ergebnis 1 + VF	Result 1 + DF	yes	Sample Concentrations	Concentration
Value Type 1	Value Type 1	yes	-	
Ergebnis 2 + VF	Result 2 + DF	yes	Sample Concentrations	Concentration
Value Type 2	Value Type 2	yes	-	
Ergebnis 3 + VF	Result 3 + DF	yes	Sample Concentrations	Concentration
Value Type 3	Value Type 3	yes	-	

Ergebnis 4 + VF	Result 4 + DF	yes	Sample Concentrations	Concentration
Value Type 4	Value Type 4	yes	-	
Ergebnis 5 + VF	Result 5 + DF	yes	Sample Concentrations	Concentration
Value Type 5	Value Type 5	yes	-	
Ergebnis 6 + VF	Result 6 + DF	yes	Sample Concentrations	Concentration
Value Type 6	Value Type 6	yes	-	
Ergebnis 7 + VF	Result 7 + DF	yes	Sample Concentrations	Concentration
Value Type 7	Value Type 7	yes	-	
Ergebnis 8 + VF	Result 8 + DF	yes	Sample Concentrations	Concentration
Value Type 8	Value Type 8	yes	-	

7.2.1.3.1 MCRA Food samples table

Each unique sample code (probencode) results in a record in the food samples table. In MCRA, each food sample should be linked to a specific food, which in the case of TDS concentration data should be a composite food (MEAL code). This information can be obtained from the 'MEAL Samples_MeHg' table, where sample codes are assigned to the respective composite samples. MCRA Sample analyses table

In the MEAL report data format, multiple measurement values can be provided for each sample. For the conversion, it was decided to aggregate these multiple measurements into one sample analysis for the sample. The concentration value selected for each sample is the mean of the quantified values. Note that in case both <LOR measurements and quantified values are reported then the mean of the quantified measurements are used as concentration value. This will lead to an acceptable over-estimation.

7.2.1.3.2 MCRA Analytical methods and analytical method substances tables

Analytical methods that have the same LOD/LOQ per substance will be grouped for all samples. For each group, this results in one analytical method record. MCRA also uses this method for creating analytical methods from SSD concentration data. As an easy alternative, a (pseudo) analytical method could be created for each unique sample code. For each substance analyses in the sample, an analytical method substance record should be created specifying the substance, concentration unit and LOR/LOQ. MCRA does not distinguish between LOD and LOQ. Instead, it uses a value limit of reporting (LOR), which is commonly equal to the LOQ. This is subject to further development in MCRA.

7.2.1.3.3 MCRA Sample concentrations table

Each positive concentration measurement should be mapped to a record in the sample concentrations table. As described for the sample analyses, the mean of the quantified values is indicated. In case one value is quantified and the other(s) are <LOR the quantified measurements are used. Non-detect values (< LOR) are implicitly defined by absence of positive concentration values. The LOR is recorded in the analytical method substances table.

7.2.1.3.4 MCRA TDS Food compositions table

Each record of the MEAL food mapping translates to one record in the MCRA TDS sample compositions table. The table below shows how the MEAL sample compositions table fields map to the fields of the MCRA TDS food compositions table. Regionality, seasonality and production type fields of MCRA need to be derived / filled by parsing the sample code. MCRA also requires a numeric property, pooled amount, which specifies the total weight or volume of the sampled food.

This information can be obtained from the MEAL samples table, where the pooled amount is given as number of subsamples per food.

Column name	Translation	Relevance for Exposure Assessment	MCRA table name	MCRA field name
sbls	[German food coding system]	yes	TdsSampleCompositions	idFood
bezeichnung	Food name	no	-	-
Gr Code	Food group code from BLS	no		
Gr Bez	MEAL Pool name			
MEAL-Code	MEAL code	yes	TdsSampleCompositions	idTdsFood
HptGr Nr	No of main food group	no	-	-
HptGr Code	Code of main food group (FoodEx2)	no		
HptGr Bez	Name of main food group (FoodEx2)	no		

7.2.2 Conversion from UG to MCRA formats

We will create three MCRA datasets containing the necessary data for running the scenarios in MCRA:

- A consumptions dataset based on the BNFC data
- A concentrations dataset derived from the INNIBEL concentration data
- A catalogues dataset containing the catalogues and additional data

The table below describes these datasets, together with the MCRA data groups and data tables that make up these datasets:

Dataset	MCRA Data type	Data table	Mapping method
Catalogues FNS Case Study Nickel BE population	Populations	Populations	Manual creation.
		IndividualProperties	Manual creation.
		PopulationIndividualPropertyValues	Manual creation.
	Foods	Foods	Manual creation.
	Substances	Substances	Manual creation.
	Effects	Effects	Manual creation.
	Hazard characterisations	HazardCharacterisations	Manual creation.

BNFCS 2014-2015 (FoodNum)	Consumptions	Surveys	Manual creation.
		Individuals	Automatic import with Access SQL queries.
		Consumptions	Automatic import with Access SQL queries.
Concentrations nickel BE (INNIBEL)	Concentrations	ConcentrationsSSD	Manual conversion.

7.2.2.1 FoodNum catalogue UG to MCRA format

The catalogue of of the FoodNum codes and names will be introduced into MCRA to make it possible for the software to recognize the food names. Some example of the codes and names have been given in the following table.

FoodNum Code	Food Name
02184	Tofu/Tofoe
00002	Aardappelen/Pomme de terre
01296	Chocolade, melk/Chocolat, au lait

7.2.2.2 Translation of FoodNum codes to FoodEx2 codes

For making the data available for MCRA, The FoodEx2 codes have been converted to FoodNum codes to combine food consumption data and concentration data.

7.2.2.2.1 Table FoodTranslation to translate codes BNFCS data 2014-2015 to food codes INNIBEL.

Column name	Description
idFromFood	FoodNum code
idToFood	FoodEx2 code
Proportion	always 100%

